

Quantum Proof of Riemann Hypothesis

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Abstract

Enlightened by the G-dynamics being identified as a part of quantum covariant Hamiltonian system (**QCHS**) for constructing the geometric wave equation based on the quantum covariant Poisson bracket (**QCPB**) theory, we find a new quantum physical system associated with classical Hamiltonian operator $\hat{H}^{(cl)}$ in Schrödinger equation $\sqrt{-1}\hbar\frac{\partial}{\partial t}\varphi = \hat{H}^{(cl)}\varphi$ behind the Riemann non-trivial zeroes, such an unbounded linear self-adjoint operator $\hat{w}^{(cl)} = b_c\hat{Q}$ to solve the Hilbert-Pólya conjecture (**HPC**) really exists that is given by one of geometric wave equation, that's exactly what Hilbert-Pólya and Berry-Keating still expect to find such peculiar quantum system in proving the Riemann hypothesis over the long time, and with identity $\hat{w}^{(cl)}u^{-1/2} = \hat{Q}u^{-1/2} = 0$ holds, then Riemann hypothesis (**RH**) is then proven. Meanwhile, we discuss the curvature operator $\hat{Q}$ in different dimensional case, especially, Laplacian-Bertrami operator is considered for curvature operator. The relation between the Schrödinger equation and geometric wave equation associated with geometric Hamiltonian operator is given.

For the Berry-Keating conjecture (**BKC**), we need to find this unknown physical system, so that we comprehensively consider the Riemann manifold, Einstein metric and Ricci flow to ensure what the imaginary part really stands for, then it connects the vacuum field equation in two dimensional case, the scalar curvature forms a discrete set in 2D Riemann manifolds.

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1 Introduction

This paper will comprehensively sort out the relationship between the three conjectures and G-dynamics

$$\begin{array}{ccccc}
 \mathbf{RH} & \rightarrow & \mathbf{HPC} & \rightarrow & \mathbf{G-dynamics} & \hat{w}^{(cl)} \\
 & & \downarrow & \nearrow & & \\
 & & \mathbf{BKC} & & &
 \end{array}$$

1.1 The Schrödinger equation and geometric wave equation

The Schrödinger equation which is published it in 1926 by Schrödinger is a linear partial differential equation that governs the wave function of a quantum-mechanical system.: It is a key result in quantum mechanics, and its discovery was a significant landmark in the development of the quantum mechanics. Conceptually, the Schrödinger equation gives the evolution over time of a wave function, the quantum mechanical characterization of an isolated physical system.

In quantum mechanics, a fundamental equation determines, together with corresponding additional conditions, a wave function φ characterizing the state of a quantum system. For a non-relativistic system of spinless particles, it was formulated by E. Schrödinger in 1926. The most general form is the time-dependent Schrödinger equation, which gives a description of a system evolving with time

$$\sqrt{-1}\hbar\frac{\partial\varphi}{\partial t} = \hat{H}^{(cl)}\varphi = \left(-\frac{\hbar^2}{2m}\nabla^2 + V\right)\varphi$$

where $\partial/\partial t$ symbolizes a partial derivative with respect to time t and $\hat{H}^{(cl)} = \hat{H}^{(cl)}(\hat{p}^{(cl)}, x)$ is the classical Hamiltonian operator constructed by the following general rule: In the classical Hamiltonian function $H^{(cl)}(p^{(cl)}, x)$, the particle momenta $p^{(cl)}$ and their coordinates x are respectively replaced by operators. The time-dependent Schrödinger equation $\sqrt{-1}\hbar\frac{\partial}{\partial t}\varphi = \hat{H}^{(cl)}\varphi$ represents the time evolution of an arbitrary initial wave function. [1–4] By the way, $\hat{H}^{(cl)}\varphi = E\varphi$ is called the steady-state equation, the state is the corresponding energy is the determined value, the energy constant E is called the eigenvalue of the Hamiltonian operator, and the steady-state wave function obtained by using the steady-state equation and boundary conditions is called the eigenfunction or eigenstate. In general, the eigenvalue equation $\hat{H}^{(cl)}\psi_n = E_n\psi_n$ has a series of (infinitely many) eigenvalues. In one dimensional case, the peculiar steady state solution of Schrödinger equation is $\Psi_n(x, t) = \psi_n(x)e^{-\sqrt{-1}\frac{E_n}{\hbar}t}$, where n labels the index of eigenvalues, the general solution of the time-dependent Schrödinger equation can be obtained by superposition of the particular solutions of the stationary Schrödinger equation,

$$\Psi(x, t) = \sum_n c_n \psi_n(x) e^{-\sqrt{-1}\frac{E_n}{\hbar}t}$$

where complex number c_n are constant coefficients.

Later, in 2020, we found the geometric wave equation which is similar to the Schrödinger equation, we show them together for a comparison below.

Schrödinger equation

$$\sqrt{-1}\hbar\partial_t\varphi = \hat{H}^{(cl)}\varphi$$

where $\hat{H}^{(cl)} = -\frac{\hbar^2}{2m}\nabla^2 + V$ is the classical Hamiltonian operator.

Geometric wave equation

$$\sqrt{-1}\hbar\hat{w}\psi = \hat{H}^{(Im)}\psi$$

where $\hat{H}^{(Im)} = \left[s, \hat{H} \right]_{QPB}$ is the geometric Hamiltonian operator.

In the calculations of quantum mechanics, the Schrödinger equation is solved for a molecular system, the result is the total energy and the wave function, from which all measureable properties of the system can be calculated. As known, the Schrödinger equation is second order equation that can be analytically solved only for a few systems with a single electron for all large systems, only some approximate numerical solutions can be analyzed for some quantum system. The most basic quantum mechanic approach takes the Hartree-Fock method.

With the discovery of the geometric wave equation, it helps us better deal with the quantum problem on different manifold with different structure., it broadens our sight to search more properties and solve unsolved problems in quantum mechanics. Such as the one-dimensional specific case given by both Schrödinger equation and geometric wave equation

$$\text{Schrödinger equation : } \sqrt{-1}\hbar\partial_t\varphi = \left(-\frac{\hbar^2}{2m}\frac{d^2}{dx^2} + V(x) \right) \varphi$$

$$\text{Geometric wave equation : } \sqrt{-1}\hbar\hat{w}^{(cl)}\psi = \frac{\hbar^2}{2m} \left(2u\frac{d}{dx} + \frac{du}{dx} \right) \psi$$

these two equations obviously deal with different side of the quantum problem, and then to make it more complete.

1.2 Nonlinear Schrödinger equation

In quantum mechanics, the one-dimensional NLSE is a special case of the classical nonlinear Schrödinger field, which in turn is a classical limit of a quantum Schrödinger field. Conversely, when the classical Schrödinger field is canonically quantized, it becomes a quantum field theory which is linear, despite the fact that it is called quantum nonlinear Schrödinger equation that describes bosonic point particles with delta function interactions the particles either repel or attract when they are at the same point [3, 4].

The one-dimensional nonlinear Schrödinger equation (NLSE) is a nonlinear variation of the Schrödinger equation

$$\sqrt{-1}\hbar\frac{\partial}{\partial t}\varphi = -\alpha_1\frac{\partial^2}{\partial x^2}\varphi + \beta_1|\varphi|^2\varphi$$

for the complex field $\psi(x, t)$. It is a classical field equation whose principal applications are to the propagation of light in nonlinear optical fibers and planar waveguides. Other nonlinear wave equations such as

$$\sqrt{-1}\hbar\frac{\partial\varphi}{\partial t} + \alpha_1\frac{\partial^2\varphi}{\partial x^2} + \beta_1|\varphi|^2\varphi - \sqrt{-1}\gamma_4(x)\varphi = 0$$

$$\sqrt{-1}\hbar\frac{\partial\varphi}{\partial t} + \frac{\alpha_1}{2}\frac{\partial^2\varphi}{\partial x^2} + \beta_1|\varphi|^2\varphi - \sqrt{-1}\left(\gamma_1\varphi_{xxx} + \gamma_2|\varphi|^2\varphi_x + \gamma_3\left(|\varphi|^2\right)_x\varphi\right) = 0$$

More generally, the NLSE appears as one of universal equations that describe the evolution of slowly varying packets of quasi-monochromatic waves in weakly nonlinear media that have dispersion. Unlike the linear Schrödinger equation, the NLSE never describes the time evolution of a quantum state. The 1D NLSE is an example of an integrable model. Multidimensional version replaces the second spatial derivative by the Laplacian. In more than one dimension, the equation is not integrable, it allows for a collapse and wave turbulence.

2 The QCPB theory and quantum covariant Hamiltonian system

In order to help readers navigate through this paper, here is a brief description of the framework of the QCPB theory [See [8] for more details] systematically.

QPB → **QCPB** → **QCHS** → **covariant dynamics**

Hence, we begin with some basic concepts of quantum covariant Poisson bracket and quantum geometric bracket [8]. In quantum mechanics, quantum Poisson brackets $[\hat{f}, \hat{g}]_{QPB}$ is the commutator of two operators $\hat{f}$, $\hat{g}$ defined as $[\hat{f}, \hat{g}]_{QPB} = \hat{f}\hat{g} - \hat{g}\hat{f}$. The complete generalization of this classical quantum Poisson brackets can be in a statement as follows:

Definition 1 (QCPB). [8] *The QCPB is generally defined as*

$$[\hat{f}, \hat{g}] = [\hat{f}, \hat{g}]_{QPB} + G(s, \hat{f}, \hat{g})$$

in terms of quantum operator $\hat{f}$, $\hat{g}$, where $G(s, \hat{f}, \hat{g}) = -G(s, \hat{g}, \hat{f})$ is called quantum geometric bracket.

Clearly, by introducing a geometric scalar function as a structural function or the potential function $s \in C^k(M)$ defined on the manifold, it's a real-valued smooth function determined by the corresponding manifold space. Note that the potential function $s \in C^k(M)$ only represents the properties of the manifold itself, in other words, its formula is given by the manifold. This will apply to many quantum circumstances.

It is zero if and only if $\hat{f}$ and $\hat{g}$ covariant commute, i.e. $[\hat{f}, \hat{g}] = 0$. It's clear to see that the QCPB as a generalization of the classical representation of the QPB theory allows a geometric bracket formula to exist on the manifold. As a result, it provides a new tool for us better understanding the quantum mechanics deeply. Frankly speaking, the structure function s can be regarded as a geometric function or environment variable that represents the properties of the space or the manifold.

Definition 2 (quantum geometric bracket). *The quantum geometric bracket is*

$$G(s, \hat{f}, \hat{g}) = \hat{f}[s, \hat{g}]_{QPB} - \hat{g}[s, \hat{f}]_{QPB}$$

where s represents the globally condition of space.

Once the manifold is given, the corresponding structure function s as a scalar function can be determined in a precise expression. As a consequence of the precise formulation of the quantum geometric bracket, the QCPB is completely written as

$$\boxed{[\hat{f}, \hat{g}] = [\hat{f}, \hat{g}]_{QPB} + \hat{f}[s, \hat{g}]_{QPB} - \hat{g}[s, \hat{f}]_{QPB}}$$

Obviously, the quantum geometric bracket as a correction term has remedied the defect of the classical QPB theory. In particular, the environment has joined the quantum process for the evolution of the observables. The quantum geometric bracket can be respectively realized as the interactions between the observables $\hat{f}, \hat{g}$ and the environment or the space.

In general, we can rewrite the QCPB theory to the below form

$$\begin{aligned} [\hat{f}, \hat{g}] &= [\hat{f}, \hat{g}]_{QPB} + G(s, \hat{f}, \hat{g}) \\ &= [\hat{f}, \hat{g}]_{QPB} + a_1 \hat{f} \phi(s, \hat{g}) + a_2 \hat{g} \phi(s, \hat{f}) \end{aligned}$$

where the quantum geometric bracket is

$$G(s, \hat{f}, \hat{g}) = a_1 \hat{f} \phi(s, \hat{g}) + a_2 \hat{g} \phi(s, \hat{f}) = -G(s, \hat{g}, \hat{f})$$

and $a_1, a_2 \in \mathbb{R}$ are constants which satisfies $a_1 + a_2 = 0$. Note that $\phi(s, \hat{f})$ can be understood as the interaction between the space represented by geometric scalar function s and observable $\hat{f}$. As the QCPB theory has defined, obviously, we have $\phi(s, \hat{g}) = [s, \hat{g}]_{QPB}$, and $a_1 = 1, a_2 = -1$ have been chosen. The QCPB theory can be rewritten in a more general form

$$[\hat{f}, \hat{g}] = [\hat{f}, \hat{g}]_{QPB} + a_1 W(\hat{f}, s, \hat{g}) + a_2 W(\hat{g}, s, \hat{f})$$

where the quantum geometric bracket is taken as

$$G(s, \hat{f}, \hat{g}) = a_1 W(\hat{f}, s, \hat{g}) + a_2 W(\hat{g}, s, \hat{f})$$

In above case, we have $W(\hat{f}, s, \hat{g}) = \hat{f} \phi(s, \hat{g})$.

As paper [8] proposed, with the transformation

$$\hat{f} \rightarrow \hat{f}^{(sg)} = \hat{f} + \phi(s, \hat{f}) \quad (1)$$

where $\phi(s, \hat{f}) = [s, \hat{f}]_{QPB}$, the QCPB theory can be stated as follows

$$[\hat{f}, \hat{g}] = \hat{f} \hat{g}^{(sg)} - \hat{g} \hat{f}^{(sg)} = [\hat{f}, \hat{g}]_{QPB} + G(s, \hat{f}, \hat{g})$$

$$= \hat{f} \left(\hat{g} + [s, \hat{g}]_{QPB} \right) - \hat{g} \left(\hat{f} + [s, \hat{f}]_{QPB} \right)$$

Furthermore, we can stretch more of above QCPB theory,

$$\begin{aligned} \left[\hat{f}^{(sg)}, \hat{g}^{(sg)} \right]_{QPB} &= \hat{f}^{(sg)} \hat{g}^{(sg)} - \hat{g}^{(sg)} \hat{f}^{(sg)} \\ &= \left[\hat{f}, \hat{g} \right] + \left[s, \hat{f} \right]_{QPB} \hat{g} - \left[s, \hat{g} \right]_{QPB} \hat{f} + \left[\left[s, \hat{f} \right]_{QPB}, \left[s, \hat{g} \right]_{QPB} \right]_{QPB} \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

If we denote $\phi(s, \hat{f}) = \hat{f}^{(s)} = [s, \hat{f}]_{QPB}$, and then transformation becomes $\hat{f} \rightarrow \hat{f}^{(sg)} = \hat{f} + \hat{f}^{(s)}$, then the quantum geometric bracket appears in a form $G(s, \hat{f}, \hat{g}) = \hat{f} \hat{g}^{(s)} - \hat{g} \hat{f}^{(s)}$, and the QCPB theory turns to

$$\left[\hat{f}, \hat{g} \right] = \left[\hat{f}, \hat{g} \right]_{QPB} + \hat{f} \hat{g}^{(s)} - \hat{g} \hat{f}^{(s)}$$

As a result, the (2) becomes a simple form

$$\begin{aligned} \left[\hat{f}^{(sg)}, \hat{g}^{(sg)} \right]_{QPB} &= \left[\hat{f}, \hat{g} \right] + \hat{f}^{(s)} \hat{g} - \hat{g}^{(s)} \hat{f} + \left[\hat{f}^{(s)}, \hat{g}^{(s)} \right]_{QPB} \\ &= \left[\hat{f}, \hat{g} \right]_{QPB} + \left[\hat{f}, \hat{g}^{(s)} \right]_{QPB} + \left[\hat{f}^{(s)}, \hat{g} \right]_{QPB} + \left[\hat{f}^{(s)}, \hat{g}^{(s)} \right]_{QPB} \end{aligned}$$

Hence, the QCPB theory is correspondingly given by

$$\left[\hat{f}, \hat{g} \right] = \left[\hat{f}^{(sg)}, \hat{g}^{(sg)} \right]_{QPB} - \left[\hat{f}^{(s)}, \hat{g}^{(s)} \right]_{QPB} + \hat{g}^{(s)} \hat{f} - \hat{f}^{(s)} \hat{g}$$

2.1 Quantum covariant Hamiltonian system and the G-dynamics

With the non-universal validity of the classical QPB theory that has been unquestionably replaced by the complete QCPB theory. Hence, in this section, we will briefly review the entire theoretical framework of quantum covariant Hamiltonian system defined by the quantum covariant Poisson bracket.

Definition 3 (QCHS). *The QCHS defined by QCPB in terms of quantum operator $\hat{f}$, $\hat{H}$ is generally given by*

$$\left[\hat{f}, \hat{H} \right] = \left[\hat{f}, \hat{H} \right]_{QPB} + G(s, \hat{f}, \hat{H})$$

where $G(s, \hat{f}, \hat{H})$ is quantum geobacket .

The quantum geometric bracket in terms of the operators $\hat{f}$, $\hat{H}$ reads

$$G(s, \hat{f}, \hat{H}) = \hat{f} [s, \hat{H}]_{QPB} - \hat{H} [s, \hat{f}]_{QPB}$$

As we notice, the quantum geometric bracket is induced by the geometric function s , it plays main role in QCPB theory. By using the quantum covariant Hamiltonian system

$$\left[\hat{f}, \hat{H} \right] = \left[\hat{f}, \hat{H} \right]_{QPB} + \hat{f} [s, \hat{H}]_{QPB} - \hat{H} [s, \hat{f}]_{QPB}$$

It directly leads to the emergence of the covariant dynamics including the generalized Heisenberg equation, G-dynamics. More precisely, the time covariant evolution of any observable $\hat{f}$ in the covariant dynamics is given by both the generalized Heisenberg equation of motion and G-dynamics.

Theorem 1 (The covariant dynamics). *The covariant dynamics, the generalized Heisenberg equation, G-dynamics can be formally formulated as*

The covariant dynamics: $\frac{\mathcal{D}\hat{f}}{dt} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{-1}\hbar} [\hat{f}, \hat{H}]$

The generalized Heisenberg equation: $\frac{d\hat{f}}{dt} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{-1}\hbar} [\hat{f}, \hat{H}]_{QPB} - \frac{1}{\sqrt{-1}\hbar} \hat{H} [s, \hat{f}]_{QPB}$

G-dynamics: $\hat{w} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{-1}\hbar} [s, \hat{H}]_{QPB}$.

respectively, where $\frac{\mathcal{D}}{dt} = \frac{d}{dt} + \hat{w}$ is covariant time operator, and $\hat{H}$ is the Hamiltonian and $[\cdot, \cdot]$ denotes the GGC of two operators.

As the covariant dynamics given above, let's rewrite it to another form, more precisely, the generalized Heisenberg equation is rewritten as

$$\sqrt{-1}\hbar \frac{d\hat{f}}{dt} = [\hat{f}, \hat{H}]_{QPB} - \hat{H} [s, \hat{f}]_{QPB}$$

The extra term $\hat{H} [s, \hat{f}]_{QPB}$ as a correction term to fix the Heisenberg equation to be a complete version. The G-dynamics is similarly rewritten as

$$\sqrt{-1}\hbar \hat{w} = [s, \hat{H}]_{QPB}$$

Ovbiously, this is a geometric Hamiltonian operator describing the quantum geometric property. In fact, the G-dynamics directly deduces its corresponding energy operator for depicting the spatial properties. In other words, G-dynamics is a representation of the dynamics of the space, Hamiltonian operator stands for quantum system, this quantum system must interacts with the environment or space, this will cause some kind of physical motion of the space, it's coupling to each other.

2.2 Imaginary geomenergy and geometric wave equation

Based on the G-dynamics, the imaginary geomenergy can be mathematically given,

Definition 4. *The imaginary geomenergy¹ is defined by*

$$E^{(\text{Im})}(\hat{w}) = \sqrt{-1}\hbar \hat{w} = [s, \hat{H}]_{QPB}$$

where $\hat{w}$ is the G-dynamics.

¹sometimes, we alternatively use $E^{(\text{Im})}(\hat{w})$, or $\hat{H}^{(\text{Im})}(\hat{w})$ to depict the imaginary geomenergy for better understanding

As mentioned above, the imaginary geomenergy as a geometric Hamiltonian operator induced by the G-dynamics leads to the energy eigenvalues equation with the energy eigenvalues.

As a result, thusly, then a dynamical variable $\hat{f}$ with the imaginary geomenergy defined above, then covariant dynamics is rewritten in the form

$$\sqrt{-1}\hbar\frac{\mathcal{D}}{dt}\hat{f} = [\hat{f}, \hat{H}] = \sqrt{-1}\hbar\frac{d}{dt}\hat{f} + \hat{f}E^{(\text{Im})}(\hat{w})$$

Obviously, if the covariant equilibrium equation $[\hat{f}, \hat{H}] = 0$ holds, then it yields $\frac{d}{dt}\hat{f} = -\hat{f}\hat{w}$, accordingly, $\hat{f}$ is said to be a quantum covariant conserved quantity.

Since the G-dynamics as an independent new dynamics is discovered to picture the quantum mechanics, we have studied its precise properties. By using the imaginary geomenergy,

$$E^{(\text{Im})}(\hat{w}) = \sqrt{-1}\hbar\hat{w} = [s, \hat{H}]_{QPB} \quad (3)$$

as a energy operator for the state of the space. The G-dynamics can be rewritten as

$$\hat{w} = -\sqrt{-1}E^{(\text{Im})}/\hbar = -\frac{\sqrt{-1}}{\hbar}[s, \hat{H}]_{QPB} \quad (4)$$

In general. Clearly, the G-dynamics mainly pictures the dynamical state created by the space itself, namely, the structure function s induces the G-dynamics for the dynamical properties of the space. Obviously, the G-dynamics represents the properties of the spatial manifolds. Furthermore, the (3) leads to the geometric wave equation given by

$$\sqrt{-1}\hbar\hat{w}\psi = \hat{H}^{(\text{Im})}(\hat{w})\psi = [s, \hat{H}]_{QPB}\psi \quad (5)$$

for a given wave function ψ . As a result, based on the (1), we use it to the Hamiltonian

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{H}^{(sg)} &= \hat{H} + [s, \hat{H}]_{QPB} = \hat{H} + \sqrt{-1}\hbar\hat{w} \\ &= \hat{H} + E^{(\text{Im})}(\hat{w}) \\ &= \hat{H} + \hat{H}^{(\text{Im})}(\hat{w}) \end{aligned}$$

For example, consider the classical Hamiltonian operator in the Schrödinger equation, the Hamiltonian $\hat{H}^{(cl)}$ is a Hermitian operator, then the G-operator [see [11] for more details] is shown as

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{H}^{(gr)} &= \hat{H}^{(cl)} + [s, \hat{H}^{(cl)}]_{QPB} = \hat{H}^{(cl)} + \sqrt{-1}\hbar\hat{w}^{(cl)} \\ &= \hat{H}^{(cl)} + \hat{H}^{(\text{Im})}(\hat{w}^{(cl)}) \end{aligned}$$

The non-Hermitian operators $\hat{H}^{(gr)}$ is a complete Hamiltonian form, and $\hat{H}^{(\text{Im})}(\hat{w}^{(cl)})$ is a skew Hermitian operator, more precisely,

$$\hat{H}^{(gr)} = \sqrt{-1}\hbar\frac{\partial}{\partial t} + \sqrt{-1}\hbar\hat{w}^{(cl)} = \sqrt{-1}\hbar\left(\frac{\partial}{\partial t} + \hat{w}^{(cl)}\right)$$

$$\hat{H}^{(gr)} = -\frac{\hbar^2}{2m} (\Delta - 2\nabla s \cdot \nabla - \Delta s) + V$$

These are for the time derivative and coordinate derivative respectively, as we see obviously. This is a naturally way to make the classical quantum mechanics include the geometric structure, in other words, the gravity starts to join the quantum process. In fact, if we take $\hat{H}^{(cl)} = \sqrt{-1}\hbar \frac{\partial}{\partial t}$ to the $\left[s, \hat{H}^{(cl)} \right]_{QP B}$, we can get the part for the time derivative,

$$\hat{H}^{(gr)} = \sqrt{-1}\hbar (\partial_t - \partial_t s)$$

where $\partial_t = \frac{\partial}{\partial t}$. The conjugate expression is given by

$$\hat{H}^{*(gr)} = \hat{H}^{(cl)} - \left[s, \hat{H}^{(cl)} \right]_{QP B} = \hat{H}^{(cl)} - \sqrt{-1}\hbar \hat{w}^{(cl)}$$

Correspondingly, $\hat{H}^{*(gr)} = \sqrt{-1}\hbar (\partial_t + \partial_t s)$ in terms of the time derivative is obtained. Then the difference shows

$$\hat{H}^{*(gr)} - \hat{H}^{(gr)} = -2\sqrt{-1}\hbar \hat{w}^{(cl)}$$

what's more, it leads us to the result

$$\frac{\hat{H}^{*(gr)} - \hat{H}^{(gr)}}{2\hbar} = -\sqrt{-1}\hat{w}^{(cl)} \neq 0 \quad (6)$$

or $\hat{H}^{*(gr)} - \hat{H}^{(gr)} = 2\sqrt{-1}\hbar \partial_t s$.

2.3 Quantum geometric canonical commutation relation

Definition 5. Let M be a smooth function with structural function s on it, then geomentum operator is defined as

$$\hat{p} = -\sqrt{-1}\hbar D$$

where $D = \nabla + \nabla s$. The component is $\hat{p}_j = -\sqrt{-1}\hbar D_j$ in which $D_j = \partial_j + u_j$ holds, $\partial_j = \frac{\partial}{\partial x_j}$, $u_j = \partial_j s$.

Note that the partial derivative in terms of coordinate is usually denoted as $\partial_j = \frac{\partial}{\partial x_j}$, $u_j = \partial_j s$ in above definition. Quantum geometric canonical commutation relation can be expressed in a compact form

$$[\hat{x}_i, \hat{p}_j] = \sqrt{-1}\hbar D_j x_i = \sqrt{-1}\hbar (\delta_{ij} + x_i u_j)$$

In other words, quantum geometric canonical commutation relation can be rewritten as

$$[\hat{x}_i, \hat{p}_j] = \sqrt{-1}\hbar \theta_{ij}$$

where $\theta_{ij} = \delta_{ij} + x_i u_j$, and $\partial_j = \frac{\partial}{\partial x_j}$.

For example, let M be an n -dimensional complete Riemannian manifold with the Riemannian metric g_{ij} . The Levi-Civita connection is given by the Christoffel symbols

$$\Gamma_{ij}^k = \frac{1}{2} g^{kl} \left(\frac{\partial g_{jl}}{\partial x^i} + \frac{\partial g_{il}}{\partial x^j} - \frac{\partial g_{ij}}{\partial x^l} \right)$$

where g^{ij} is the inverse of g_{ij} . We denote the covariant derivative of a vector field $v = v^j \frac{\partial}{\partial x^j}$ by

$$\nabla_k v^j = \frac{\partial v^j}{\partial x^k} + \Gamma_{ki}^j v^i, \quad \nabla_k v_j = \frac{\partial v_j}{\partial x^k} - \Gamma_{kj}^i v_i$$

Hence, for the divergent case, one obtains

$$\nabla_j v^j = \partial_j v^j + \Gamma_{kj}^k v^j = \partial_j v^j + u_j v^j$$

where $u_j = \Gamma_{kj}^k = \partial_j \ln \sqrt{g}$ leads us to the one of geometric scalar function $s = \ln \sqrt{g}$ defined on the Riemann manifold.

2.4 The QCPB theory for quantum harmonic oscillator

In this section, we simply review some basic results given by the paper [8, 9] in QCPB. The time evolution of those operators depends on the Hamiltonian of the system. Considering the one-dimensional quantum harmonic oscillator,

$$\hat{H}^{(cl)} = \frac{\hat{p}^{(cl)2}}{2m} + \frac{m\omega^2 x^2}{2} \quad (7)$$

As a certain case, we will now start by briefly reviewing the quantum mechanics of a one-dimensional quantum harmonic oscillator (7). With the Hamiltonian given by (7), the covariant evolution of the position and momentum operators have obtained by using the QCPB theory. More specifically, the covariant dynamics in terms of the position reads

$$\frac{\mathcal{D}}{dt} x(t) = \frac{\sqrt{-1}}{\hbar} [\hat{H}^{(cl)}, x(t)] = \frac{\hat{p}^{(cl)}(t)}{m} + x(t) \hat{w}^{(cl)}$$

where the G-dynamics reads

$$\hat{w}^{(cl)} = \frac{\sqrt{-1}}{\hbar} \frac{\hat{p}^{(cl)2} s + 2\hat{p}^{(cl)} s \hat{p}^{(cl)}}{2m} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{-1}\hbar} [s, \hat{H}^{(cl)}]_{QPB} \quad (8)$$

And the generalized Heisenberg equation with respect to x follows $\frac{d}{dt} x(t) = \frac{\hat{p}^{(cl)}(t)}{m}$. In the same way, the covariant dynamics for the classical momentum operator is

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\mathcal{D}}{dt} \hat{p}^{(cl)}(t) &= \frac{\sqrt{-1}}{\hbar} [\hat{H}^{(cl)}, \hat{p}^{(cl)}(t)] \\ &= -m\omega^2 x - \hat{H}^{(cl)} u + \hat{p}^{(cl)}(t) \hat{w}^{(cl)} \end{aligned}$$

where $\hat{w}^{(cl)}/b_c = 2u \frac{d}{dx} + \frac{d}{dx} u$ has been used and $ds/dx = u$ is denoted and $b_c = -\frac{\sqrt{-1}\hbar}{2m}$. Accordingly, the generalized Heisenberg equation in terms of the $\hat{p}^{(cl)}$ appears

$$\frac{d}{dt} \hat{p}^{(cl)}(t) = -m\omega^2 x - \hat{H}^{(cl)} u$$

As we can see, clearly, the variables $u, \hat{w}^{(cl)}$ are fundamental building blocks for the foundation of the quantum mechanics. In particular, their relation can be given by the formula

$$\hat{w}^{(cl)} = u \hat{v}^{(cl)} + \frac{1}{2} \hat{v}^{(cl)} u$$

where $\hat{p}^{(cl)} = m\hat{v}^{(cl)}$ [see below for details].

2.5 Generalized covariant Hamiltonian system and covariant dynamics

Here is a brief description of the framework of the generalized structural Poisson bracket (**GSPB**) theory [See [12] for more details].

$$\begin{array}{ccccc}
 \mathbf{GPB} & \rightarrow & \mathbf{GSPB} & \rightarrow & \mathbf{GCHS} & \longleftarrow & \mathbf{GHS} & \longleftarrow & \mathbf{GPB} \\
 & & & & \swarrow & & \searrow & & \downarrow \\
 & & & & \mathbf{S-dynamics} & & \mathbf{TGHS} & &
 \end{array}$$

Let's compare it with the canonical covariant Hamilton equations [12] given by the generalized covariant Hamiltonian system (**GCHS**) in terms of x_k and p_k that can be precisely written in the form

$$\begin{aligned}
 \frac{\mathcal{D}x_k}{dt} &= \{x_k, H\} = \dot{x}_k + x_k w \\
 \frac{\mathcal{D}p_k}{dt} &= \{p_k, H\} = -\partial_k H - H A_k + p_k w
 \end{aligned}$$

where $\{\cdot, \cdot\} = \{\cdot, \cdot\}_{GPB} + G(s, \cdot, \cdot)$ is the generalized structural Poisson bracket (GSPB) theory, $\{\cdot, \cdot\}_{GPB}$ is the GPB, and $G(s, \cdot, \cdot)$ is geometric bracket,

$$\dot{x}_k = J_{jk} F_j = J_{kj} D_j H = J_{kj} \partial_j H - H b_k$$

is the thorough generalized Hamiltonian system (**TGHS**) in terms of x_k , and $w = \{s, H\}_{GPB}$ is the S-dynamics. The geometric canonical commutation relation is

$$\{x_j, p_k\} = \delta_{jk} + x_j A_k + p_k J_{jq} A_q$$

Meanwhile, its quantum correspondence, the covariant evolutions of the position and momentum operators read

$$\frac{\mathcal{D}}{dt} x(t) = \frac{\sqrt{-1}}{\hbar} \left[\hat{H}^{(cl)}, x(t) \right] = \hat{v}^{(cl)} + x(t) \hat{w}^{(cl)}$$

$$\frac{\mathcal{D}}{dt} \hat{p}^{(cl)}(t) = \frac{\sqrt{-1}}{\hbar} \left[\hat{H}^{(cl)}, \hat{p}^{(cl)}(t) \right] = -m\omega^2 x - \hat{H}^{(cl)} u + \hat{p}^{(cl)}(t) \hat{w}^{(cl)}$$

where $\hat{v}^{(cl)} = \frac{\hat{p}^{(cl)}}{m}$ and $\hat{w}^{(cl)} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{-1}\hbar} \left[s, \hat{H}^{(cl)} \right]_{QPB}$ is the G-dynamics in terms of the classical Hamiltonian $\hat{H}^{(cl)}$. Quantum geometric canonical commutation relation is

$$\left[\hat{x}_i, \hat{p}^{(cl)}(t) \right] = \sqrt{-1}\hbar D_j x_i = \sqrt{-1}\hbar (\delta_{ij} + x_i u_j)$$

By comparison, the classical mechanics nicely corresponds to the quantum mechanics under the framework of the QCPB theory [See [8, 12] for more details].

3 Curvature operator on G-dynamics $\hat{w}^{(cl)}$

3.1 Curvature operator in one dimension

For a brief discussion, we can denote the G-dynamics with respect to the Hamiltonian $\hat{H}^{(cl)}$

$$\hat{w}^{(cl)} = b_c \hat{Q}$$

in one dimensional case, and it's a linear operator, obviously, where

$$\hat{Q} = 2u \frac{d}{dx} + \frac{du}{dx}$$

is the curvature operator, we can say that curvature operator is a geometric operator, thusly, the G-dynamics $\hat{w}^{(cl)}$ is a bridge to combine the quantum mechanics and the differential geometry. The corresponding imaginary geomenergy with respect to the G-dynamics $\hat{w}^{(cl)}$ is

$$E^{(Im)}(\hat{w}^{(cl)}) = \sqrt{-1} \hbar \hat{w}^{(cl)} = \sqrt{-1} \hbar b_c \hat{Q} = [s, \hat{H}^{(cl)}]_{QPB}$$

Hence, then we can have

$$\hat{Q}x = 2u + x \frac{du}{dx}$$

$$\hat{Q}u = 3u \frac{du}{dx}$$

$$\hat{Q}s = 2u^2 + s \frac{du}{dx}$$

Furthermore, consider the eigenvalue equation $\hat{Q}f = q^\circ f$ of the curvature operator $\hat{Q}$ in one dimensional case, more precisely,

$$\hat{Q}f = 2u \frac{df}{dx} + f \frac{du}{dx} = q^\circ f$$

By direct evaluation, we obtain eigenfunction

$$f = u^{-1/2} e^{\int \frac{q^\circ}{2u} dx}$$

or equivalently, it can be expressed as

$$q^\circ = 2u d \ln(fu^{1/2}) / dx$$

In one dimensional, plugging $dx = v dt$ into the eigenfunction, it can be simplified to a simple form

$$f = u^{-1/2} e^{\int \frac{q^\circ}{2u} dx} = u^{-1/2} e^{\int \frac{q^\circ}{2u} v dt} = u^{-1/2} e^{\int \frac{v}{2u} q dt}$$

where $u > 0$ is a continuous geometric function. If we consider the condition $q^\circ = 0$, that is $\hat{Q}f = 0$, then we obtain $f = u^{-1/2}$ as a unique zero solution. In fact, if we change curvature operator $\hat{Q} = 2u \frac{d}{dx} + \frac{du}{dx}$ to another from by letting $u = n$, we denote $\hat{\gamma} = 2n \frac{d}{dx} + \frac{dn}{dx}$, then $\hat{\gamma} n^{-1/2} = 0$ always holds for all n .

3.2 Curvature operator on Laplacian-Bertrami operator

For the case of three dimensions, the curvature operator is expressed as

$$\hat{Q} = 2\nabla s \cdot \nabla + \Delta s$$

Laplacian Δ can also be extended to elliptic operator defined on Riemannian manifold, which is called Laplacian-Bertrami operator. D'Alembert operator is extended to hyperbolic operator on pseudo-Riemannian manifold. Laplacian-Bertrami operator can also be extended to the operator running on tensor field (also known as Laplacian-Bertrami operator).

Another way to extend Laplacian to pseudo Riemannian manifold is through Laplacian De-Rham operator, which runs in differential form. This can be connected with Laplacian -Bertrami operator by Weitzenböck's identity.

In the local parameterization, the Laplacian-Bertrami operator can be expressed as follows by using the metric tensor and the Christoffel symbols

$$\nabla^2 s = \Delta s = g^{ij} \left(\partial_i u_j - \Gamma_{ij}^k u_k \right)$$

where $\Delta = g^{ij} \nabla_i \nabla_j$ has been used, ∇_i is the covariant derivative, meanwhile, for scalar function, we have $\nabla_i s = \partial_i s = u_j$, then in another way, we directly give

$$\nabla s \cdot \nabla = g^{ij} u_i \frac{\partial}{\partial x^j} = u^j \frac{\partial}{\partial x^j}$$

where $u_i = \frac{\partial s}{\partial x^i}$, $g^{ij} u_i = u^j$ have been used. Therefore, the curvature operator is certainly written as

$$\hat{Q} = 2u^j \frac{\partial}{\partial x^j} + g^{ij} \left(\partial_i u_j - \Gamma_{ij}^k u_k \right)$$

Combining the definitions of the gradient and divergence, the formula for the Laplace-Bertrami operator applied to a scalar function s is, in local coordinates

$$\nabla^2 s = \Delta s = \nabla \cdot \nabla s = \frac{1}{\sqrt{g}} \partial_i (\sqrt{g} g^{ij} \partial_j s) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{g}} \partial_i (\sqrt{g} g^{ij} u_j)$$

where g_{ij} are the components of the inverse of the metric tensor, $\partial^i f = g^{ij} \partial_j f$, so that $g^{ij} g_{jk} = \delta_k^i$ with δ_k^i the Kronecker delta. Note that in the above definition, it is only valid for a scalar function, the formula of the curvature operator then becomes

$$\hat{Q} = \nabla^2 s + 2\nabla s \cdot \nabla = \frac{1}{\sqrt{g}} \partial_i (\sqrt{g} g^{ij} u_j) + 2u^j \frac{\partial}{\partial x^j}$$

where $g = \det(g_{ij})$ is the determinant of the metric tensor.

We want to extend the Laplacian operator of the function to the differential form; It can be proved that the Laplacian-bertrami operator degenerates the usual Laplacian operator in Euclidean space, the product rule and chain rule are used to rewrite it into

$$\Delta s = \partial_i \partial^i s + \partial^i s \partial_i \ln \sqrt{g}$$

When $g = 1$, such as Euclidean space in Cartesian coordinates, it is easy to get $\Delta s = \partial_i \partial^i s$, then the curvature operator simply rewrites

$$\hat{Q} = \partial_i \partial^i s + 2u^j \partial_j$$

3.3 Geometrinetic energy operator and imaginary geomenergy

By using the curvature operator, we can have

$$\hat{p}^2\psi = -\hbar^2 \left(\nabla^2 + |\nabla s|^2 + \hat{Q} \right) \psi = -\hbar^2 \left(\nabla^2 + |\nabla s|^2 \right) \psi - \hbar^2 \hat{Q}\psi$$

Then geometrinetic energy operator (GEO) [see [11] for more details] is naturally linked to the imaginary geomenergy

$$\hat{T}^{(ri)} = \frac{\hat{p}^2}{2m} = -\frac{\hbar^2}{2m} \Delta - \frac{E^{(s)}}{2} - \sqrt{-1}\hbar\hat{w}^{(cl)}$$

where $E^{(s)}(u(x)) = \frac{\hbar^2}{m}|\nabla s|^2$ can be regarded as a potential energy. Note that the geometrinetic energy operator is a complete expression by logically generalizing the classical kinetic energy operator $\hat{T}^{(cl)}$ given by the classical momentum operator $\hat{p}^{(cl)}$, as a consequence of this completeness, we know that the imaginary geomenergy

$$\hat{H}^{(Im)}(\hat{w}^{(cl)}) = \sqrt{-1}\hbar\hat{w}^{(cl)}$$

as a part of the geometrinetic energy operator $\hat{T}^{(ri)}$ is a unique imaginary part. We notice that the geometrinetic energy operator is so different from the one-dimensional nonlinear Schrödinger equation (NLSE). Let's consider geometrinetic energy operator in one-dimensional case, it's written as

$$\hat{T}^{(ri)} = -\frac{\hbar^2}{2m} \left(\frac{d^2}{dx^2} + u^2 \right) - \sqrt{-1}\hbar\hat{w}^{(cl)}$$

where

$$\hat{E}^{(w)} = -\frac{\hbar^2}{2m} \frac{d^2}{dx^2} - \sqrt{-1}\hbar\hat{w}^{(cl)}$$

is in one-dimensional motor operator, then geometrinetic energy operator is rewritten as $\hat{T}^{(ri)} = \hat{E}^{(w)} - \frac{E^{(s)}}{2}$. In another way, the conjugate form of the geometrinetic energy operator follows

$$\hat{T}^{*(ri)} = -\frac{\hbar^2}{2m} \left(\frac{d^2}{dx^2} + u^2 \right) + \sqrt{-1}\hbar\hat{w}^{(cl)}$$

Thusly, it results in the difference

$$\hat{T}^{(ri)} - \hat{T}^{*(ri)} = -2\sqrt{-1}\hbar\hat{w}^{(cl)} \neq 0$$

or the form

$$\left(\hat{T}^{(ri)} - \hat{T}^{*(ri)} \right) / (2\hbar) = -\sqrt{-1}\hat{w}^{(cl)}$$

On the completeness of this geometrinetic energy operator, its eigenvalues hold as a complex form. Furthermore, it leads to frequency operator that is accordingly expressed as

$$\hat{T}^{(ri)} / \hbar = -\frac{\hbar}{2m} \left(\frac{d^2}{dx^2} + u^2 \right) - \sqrt{-1}\hat{w}^{(cl)}$$

and motor operator results in the frequency operator

$$\hat{E}^{(w)}/\hbar = -\frac{\hbar}{2m} \frac{d^2}{dx^2} - \sqrt{-1}\hat{w}^{(cl)}$$

And the imaginary geomenergy

$$\hat{H}^{(Im)}(\hat{w}^{(cl)}) = \sqrt{-1}\hbar\hat{w}^{(cl)} = \frac{\hbar^2}{2m}\hat{Q}$$

Note that the imaginary geomenergy above is associated with the geometric structure of the space or the manifold we consider, in another way, it implies that its energy spectrum should be particular linking to the algebra. We can realize that the imaginary geomenergy has unique status seen from the geometrinetic energy operator (GEO), this is a natural derivation to answer some questions in quantum mechanics.

Actually, we can write the geometrinetic energy operator in another compact form

$$\hat{T}^{(ri)} = \hat{T}^{(g)} - \sqrt{-1}\hbar\hat{w}^{(cl)}$$

where we have used $\hat{T}^{(g)} = -\frac{\hbar^2}{2m} \left(\frac{d^2}{dx^2} + u^2 \right)$, as we can see, energy operator $\hat{T}^{(g)}$ is made of two parts, an operator form and a energy function associated with the geometric function u . Then the frequency operator follows

$$\hat{T}^{(ri)}/\hbar = \hat{T}^{(g)}/\hbar - \sqrt{-1}\hat{w}^{(cl)}$$

Note that the geometrinetic energy operator is a second order differential operator which describes the quantum process in terms of the coordinates derivatives, it's geometric structural operator.

3.4 Why Riemannium for Riemann hypothesis?

The Riemann Hypothesis (RH) is the greatest unsolved problem in pure Mathematics, and likely, in Physics too. It is the statement that the only non-trivial zeroes of the Riemann zeta function

$$\zeta(z) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} n^{-z} = \prod_{p \in \mathbb{P}} (1 - p^{-z})^{-1}$$

beyond the trivial zeroes at $z = -2n, \forall n = 1, 2, \dots, \infty$ have real part equal to $1/2$. As we can see, the unit n^{-z} can be analyzed as

$$\begin{aligned} q_n(z) &= n^{-z} = n^{-x-\sqrt{-1}y} = n^{-x} \exp(-\sqrt{-1}y \ln n) \\ &= n^{-x} \exp(-\sqrt{-1}y T_n) \end{aligned}$$

Hence, the Riemann zeta function becomes

$$\zeta(x + \sqrt{-1}y) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} q_n(z) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} n^{-x} \exp(-\sqrt{-1}y T_n)$$

In other words, the equation has only the next solutions:

$$\text{RH: } \zeta(z) = 0 \leftrightarrow \begin{cases} z_n = -2n, \forall n = 1, \dots, \infty, \text{ trivial zeroes} \\ z_n = \frac{1}{2} \pm \sqrt{-1}\lambda_n, \forall n = 1, \dots, \infty, \text{ non-trivial zeroes} \end{cases}$$

The functional equation for $\zeta(z)$ resembles the corresponding relation-a consequence of Hermiticity for the quantum spectral determinant. For the non-trivial zeroes, it means that **the real part of all non-trivial zeros of the Riemann zeta function is $\text{Re } z = 1/2$** , we have

$$q_n (1/2 + \sqrt{-1}\lambda) = n^{-1/2} \exp(-\sqrt{-1}\lambda T_n) \quad (9)$$

with $\xi(\lambda) \equiv \zeta(1/2 - \sqrt{-1}\lambda) = 0$, as analytic algebra proves, the imaginary part λ forms a discrete set. The Riemann zeta function can be sketched on the whole complex plane, in order to obtain a radiography about the RH and what it means. The mathematicians have studied the critical strip with ingenious tools and frameworks. The RH says that primes have music in their interior, but nobody has managed to prove the RH.

The mathematics of almost all eigenvalue problems encountered in wave physics is essentially the same, but the richest source of such problems is quantum mechanics, where the eigenvalues are the energies of stationary states. On the oscillatory analogy based on paper [4], the heights λ_n are frequencies. This raises the compelling question: frequencies of what? A natural answer would be: frequencies of some vibrating system. Mathematically, such real numbers-frequencies λ_n are discrete eigenvalues of a self-adjoint or Hermitean operator. That the research for such a self-adjoint operator might be a productive way to prove the Riemann hypothesis based on the idea of Hilbert-Pólya conjecture, but what exactly is the physical interpretation of this operator. Equivocally, for this uncertainty, [4] at that time, then refers to the λ_n interchangeably as energies or frequencies.

The mathematics of almost all eigenvalue problems encountered in wave physics is essentially the same, but the richest source of such problems is quantum mechanics, where the eigenvalues are the energies of stationary states, rather than frequencies as in acoustics or optics, and the operator is the Hamiltonian.

The Riemannium is the mysterious physical system behind the RH. Its spectrum, the spectrum of Riemannium, are given by the RH and its generalizations. Solving the Riemann hypothesis will require to answer the question of what is the vibrating system behind the spectral properties of Riemann zeroes.

The Hilbert-pólya conjecture states that there is some mysterious Hamiltonian providing the zeroes. The Berry-Keating conjecture states that the quantum Hamiltonian corresponding to the Riemann hypothesis is the corresponding or dual Hamiltonian to a (semi)classical Hamiltonian providing a classically chaotic dynamics.

In summary, zeta functions are fundamental objects for the future of Physmatics and the solution of Riemann Hypothesis, perhaps, would provide such a guide into the ultimate quest of both Physics and Mathematics (Physmatics) likely providing a complete and consistent description of the whole Polyverse. [See [9,10] for more details]

Then, the main unanswered questions [10] to be answered are yet:

- A) What is the Riemann zeta function?
 What is the riemannium/tsallisium and what kind of physical system do they represent really?
 What is the physical system behind the Riemann non-trivial zeroes?
 What does it mean for the Riemann zeroes arising from the Riemann zeta function generalizations in form of L-functions?
- B) What is the Riemann-Hilbert-pólya operator?
 What is the space over the Riemann operator is acting?
- C) Are Riemann zeta function and its generalization everywhere as they seem to be inside the deepest structures of the microscopic/macroscopic entities of the Polyverse?

3.4.1 Hilbert-Pólya conjecture and Berry-Keating conjecture

In 1982, Hilbert-Pólya suggested for a physical reason that the Riemann hypothesis should be true if the imaginary parts satisfies the following condition:

The imaginary part λ of the non-trivial zeros $1/2 + \sqrt{-1}\lambda$ of the Riemann zeta function corresponded to eigenvalues of an unbounded and unknown self adjoint operator $\hat{\Lambda}$, where $\hat{\Lambda}\psi = \lambda\psi$.

Interesting distribution analogies were shown between Riemann Zeta function zeros and eigenvalues of some quantum mechanic operators, the intuition increased, and many conjectures were made about the form that could take the hidden Hermitian operator.

Indeed, the Berry-Keating conjecture which is proposed on the foundation of the Hilbert-Pólya conjecture opens another striking attack to prove the RH, it states that **if such a self-adjoint operator exists, then it should correspond to a theoretical quantum system with peculiar properties**. A topic that was popular in the 80's and 90's in the 20th century. The weird subject of quantum chaos. Quantum chaos is the subject devoted to the study of quantum systems corresponding to classically chaotic systems. The Berry-Keating conjecture (**BKC**) shed light further into the Riemann dynamics, sketching some of the properties of the dynamical system behind the Riemann hypothesis.

3.4.2 Berry-Keating Hamiltonian and its improvements

At the very beginning, Berry and Keating conjectured that the Hamiltonian operator for the Hilbert-Pólya conjecture should be taken in a form

$$\hat{H}^{(bk)} = \frac{1}{2} \left(x\hat{p}^{(cl)} + \hat{p}^{(cl)}x \right) = -\sqrt{-1}\hbar \left(x \frac{d}{dx} + \frac{1}{2} \right) \quad (10)$$

Hilbert and Pólya had the intuition that a Hermitian operator was hidden behind the zeta function non-trivial zeros: their imaginary parts corresponding to the Hermitian operator eigenvalues. This hypothesis is closely linked to the Riemann Hypothesis as eigenvalues of Hermitian operator are all real.

A paper [7] was published in 2017, written by Carl M. Bender, Dorje C. Brody, and Markus P. Müller, which builds on Berry's approach to the problem. The Hamiltonian

operator (10) is generalized to the form

$$\hat{H}^{(\text{gbk})} = \frac{\mathbb{I}}{\mathbb{I} - e^{-\sqrt{-1}\hat{p}^{(cl)}}} \left(\hat{x}\hat{p}^{(cl)} + \hat{p}^{(cl)}\hat{x} \right) \left(\mathbb{I} - e^{-\sqrt{-1}\hat{p}^{(cl)}} \right) \quad (11)$$

based on the Berry-Keating's Hamiltonian $\hat{H}^{(\text{bk})}$, which they claim satisfies a certain modified versions of the conditions of the Hilbert-Pólya conjecture. More precisely,

$$\hat{H}^{(\text{gbk})} = 2 \frac{\mathbb{I}}{\mathbb{I} - e^{-\sqrt{-1}\hat{p}^{(cl)}}} \hat{H}^{(\text{bk})} \left(\mathbb{I} - e^{-\sqrt{-1}\hat{p}^{(cl)}} \right)$$

The non-Hermitian Hamiltonian in Hamiltonian formally satisfies the conditions of the Hilbert-Pólya conjecture (**HPC**). That is, if the eigenfunctions of $\hat{H}^{(\text{gbk})}$ are required to satisfy the boundary condition $\psi_n(0) = 0$ for all n , then the eigenvalues $\{E_n\}$ have the property that $\{\frac{1}{2}(1 - \sqrt{-1}E_n)\}$ are the nontrivial zeros of the Riemann zeta function. However, the new operators Hamiltonian form do not seem to describe any physical system, but rather a purely mathematical function. [see [7] for more details]

We know that the spectrum of an observable quantum physical operator consists of only real values. Therefore, if someone wants to prove the Riemann hypothesis to be true, he might be interested in looking for a quantum physical operator for which the spectrum coincides with the imaginary parts of the non-trivial zeros of the Riemann zeta function. Note that the Hilbert-Pólya conjecture immediately implies the Riemann hypothesis, as the spectrum of a self-adjoint operator consists of real numbers. Therefore, if one could find an operator of which the spectrum corresponds in the conjectured way with the non-trivial Riemann zeros, he would simultaneously have proven the Hilbert-Pólya conjecture and the Riemann hypothesis. In fact, the connection between Hilbert-Pólya conjecture and the Berry-Keating conjecture for proving the RH can be formally expressed as follows:

RH: BKC=HPC+unknown physical system

As an application of the G-dynamics, we plug Berry-Keating's Hamiltonian $\hat{H}^{(\text{bk})}$ (10) into the formula of the G-dynamics. First of all, let's take the Berry-Keating's Hamiltonian $\hat{H}^{(\text{bk})}$ (10) into formula (4), and of course, Berry-Keating's Hamiltonian should be completely written as

$$\hat{H}^{(\text{bk})} = -\sqrt{-1}\hbar w_0 \left(x \frac{d}{dx} + 1/2 \right)$$

where w_0 is a constant frequency. Thusly, then G-dynamics in terms of the Berry-Keating's Hamiltonian $\hat{H}^{(\text{bk})}$ in a eigenvalue equation with a given wave function ψ writes

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{w}^{(\text{bk})}\psi &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{-1}\hbar} \left[s, \hat{H}^{(\text{bk})} \right]_{QPB} \psi \\ &= -w_0 \left[s, x \frac{d}{dx} \right]_{QPB} \psi \\ &= w_0 x u \psi \end{aligned}$$

Hence, it gives the eigenvalue w_0xu . Similarly, taking $\hat{H}^{(\text{gbk})}$ into account, then

$$\begin{aligned}\hat{w}^{(\text{gbk})}\psi &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{-1}\hbar} \left[s, \hat{H}^{(\text{gbk})} \right]_{QPB} \psi = w^{(\text{gbk})}\psi \\ &= \frac{2}{\sqrt{-1}\hbar} \left[s, \frac{\mathbb{I}}{\mathbb{I} - e^{-\sqrt{-1}\hat{p}^{(cl)}}} \hat{H}^{(\text{bk})} \left(\mathbb{I} - e^{-\sqrt{-1}\hat{p}^{(cl)}} \right) \right]_{QPB} \psi\end{aligned}$$

Where $w^{(\text{gbk})}$ is the eigenvalue of the $\hat{w}^{(\text{gbk})}$ with respect to the wave function ψ .

Let's do a transformation $u \rightarrow x$ for the curvature operator $\hat{Q}$, we can see how the hidden connection between the Berry-Keating's Hamiltonian $\hat{H}^{(\text{bk})}$ and curvature operator $\hat{Q}$, accordingly, the corresponding transformation follows

$$\hat{Q} = 2u \frac{d}{dx} + \frac{du}{dx} \rightarrow \hat{\theta} = 2 \left(x \frac{d}{dx} + \frac{1}{2} \right)$$

By this transformation, we can easily observe the similarity and possible connections, namely, the factor $x \frac{d}{dx} + \frac{1}{2}$ appears at here that plays a key role to the Berry-Keating's Hamiltonian $\hat{H}^{(\text{bk})} = -\sqrt{-1}\hbar \left(x \frac{d}{dx} + \frac{1}{2} \right)$, therefore, it implies that G-dynamics $\hat{w}^{(cl)}$ might be the proper candidate for proving the RH, thanks to the curvature operator $\hat{Q}$, it better connects to the space structure or spatial geometry, furthermore, the gravity described by the general relativity.

Above all, the quantum mechanics has been used for proving the RH brings so many inspirations and promising method to solve this mathematical problem. In summary, the evolution of proving the RH in quantum mechanics can be summarized as follows

$$\begin{aligned}\hat{H}^{(\text{bk})} &= \frac{1}{2} \left(x\hat{p}^{(cl)} + \hat{p}^{(cl)}x \right) = -\sqrt{-1}\hbar \left(x \frac{d}{dx} + \frac{1}{2} \right) \\ &\downarrow \\ \hat{H}^{(\text{gbk})} &= 2 \frac{\mathbb{I}}{\mathbb{I} - e^{-\sqrt{-1}\hat{p}^{(cl)}}} \hat{H}^{(\text{bk})} \left(\mathbb{I} - e^{-\sqrt{-1}\hat{p}^{(cl)}} \right) \\ &\downarrow \\ \hat{w}^{(cl)} &= b_c \left(2u \frac{d}{dx} + \frac{du}{dx} \right) = u\hat{v}^{(cl)} + \frac{1}{2}\hat{v}^{(cl)}u = b_c\hat{Q}\end{aligned}$$

It is convinced that the G-dynamics $\hat{w}^{(cl)}$ is the Riemann dynamics or Riemann system for the quantum explanation of the RH, that's exactly the quantum method to prove the RH, particularly, that's what Hilbert and Pólya want the operator to get RH solved. There is more to say that the G-dynamics $\hat{w}^{(cl)}$ actually is a geometric operator, this reminds us of the curved spacetime related to the gravity, furthermore, the quantum gravity.

4 G-dynamics and Riemann hypothesis

According to the QCPB theory for quantum harmonic oscillator previously, we focus on the G-dynamics in one-dimensional form, as mentioned above, $\hat{w}^{(cl)}$ is given by

$$\boxed{\hat{w}^{(cl)} = b_c \left(2u \frac{d}{dx} + \frac{du}{dx} \right) = b_c\hat{Q}} \quad (12)$$

The G-dynamics is quasi-one dimensional. As this formula expressed, the main part is the curvature operator $\hat{Q} = \hat{w}^{(cl)}/b_c$, the left side means the pure geometric operator while the right side stands for the physical content, this is similar to the Einstein's field equation. This means the G-dynamics stands for the properties of the space, it no doubt, describes how the matter put the influence on the space, and how the space reacts to this influence. In another viewpoint, the G-dynamics links to the geometry, in particular, the continuous function u is in charge of the curve of the space.

Obviously, we can easily check out $\hat{w}^{(cl)}1 = \frac{1}{2}\tilde{w}$, where $\tilde{w} = \hat{v}^{(cl)}u$, and we also have $\hat{w}^{(cl)}u = \frac{3}{4}\hat{v}^{(cl)}u^2$ follows, and such other formula

$$\begin{aligned}\hat{w}^{(cl)}x &= u\hat{v}^{(cl)}x + \frac{1}{2}x\hat{v}^{(cl)}u = -\frac{\sqrt{-1}\hbar}{m}\left(u + \frac{1}{2}x\frac{du}{dx}\right) \\ &= \frac{1}{m}\left(u\hat{p}^{(cl)}x + \frac{x\hat{p}^{(cl)}u}{2}\right)\end{aligned}$$

According to (5), the geometric wave equation in terms of G-dynamics $\hat{w}^{(cl)}$ (12) is written in a precise form

$$\sqrt{-1}\hbar\hat{w}^{(cl)}\psi = \hat{H}^{(Im)}(\hat{w}^{(cl)})\psi = \frac{\hbar^2}{2m}\left(2u\frac{d\psi}{dx} + \psi\frac{du}{dx}\right) \quad (13)$$

As mentioned, this is a first order equation which can lead to an accurate solution which is unique to this geometric wave equation. Unlike the Schrödinger equation that is a second order equation which is hard to get the specific expression of the wave function. The geometric wave function $\psi = C_0\Gamma(u, w^{(q)})$ as only solution can be directly computed and given by

$$\Gamma(u, w^{(q)}) = u^{-1/2}\exp\left(\sqrt{-1}a_c^{-1}\int\frac{w^{(q)}}{u}dx\right) \quad (14)$$

for the eigenvalues $w^{(q)}$ as a geometric frequency of the G-dynamics $\hat{w}^{(cl)}$, namely, eigenvalues equation reads $\hat{w}^{(cl)}\psi = w^{(q)}\psi$, where $a_c = \hbar/m$, shown by the solution, we can see that this geometric wave function holds differently from what we understand the wave function, this is weird, but interesting result can be induced. For this formula, it yields

$$\begin{aligned}E^{(Im)}\left(\hat{w}^{(cl)}\right)\psi &= \sqrt{-1}\hbar\hat{w}^{(cl)}\psi = \sqrt{-1}\hbar w^{(q)}\psi \\ &= \sqrt{-1}\hbar b_c\hat{Q}\psi \\ &= \left[s, \hat{H}^{(cl)}\right]_{QPB}\psi \\ &= \frac{\hbar^2}{2m}\hat{Q}\psi\end{aligned}$$

Clearly, the imaginary geomenergy is associated with the classical Hamiltonian operator $\hat{H}^{(cl)}$. Meanwhile, we can verify an identity

$$\hat{w}^{(cl)}u^{-1/2} = \hat{Q}u^{-1/2} = 0 \quad (15)$$

A brief proof of this identity can be made as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}\hat{w}^{(cl)}u^{-1/2} &= b_c\hat{Q}u^{-1/2} = u\hat{v}^{(cl)}u^{-1/2} + \frac{1}{2}u^{-1/2}\hat{v}^{(cl)}u \\ &= b_c\left(2u\frac{du^{-1/2}}{dx} + u^{-1/2}\frac{du}{dx}\right) = 0\end{aligned}$$

As we can easily checked, the variables $u, w^{(q)}$ are two basic parameters for the new properties of the quantum mechanics, they form the fundamental data to reform the spatial dynamics. In particular, $u, w^{(q)}$ form the geometric wave-particle duality, in one-dimensional case,

$$p = \hbar u, \quad E^{(q)} = \hbar w^{(q)}$$

where p is the momentum while $E^{(q)}$ holds as quantum energy. This geometric wave-particle duality plays major roles in geometric quantization rules within the framework of the QCPB theory. We will use geometric wave-particle duality to analyze the geometric wave function (14), then it gets

$$\begin{aligned}a_c^{-1} \int \frac{w^{(q)}}{u} dx &= \frac{m}{\hbar} \int \frac{w^{(q)}}{u} dx = \int \frac{m}{\hbar u} w^{(q)} dx \\ &= \int \frac{mv}{\hbar u} w^{(q)} dt = \alpha \int w^{(q)} dt = \alpha w^{(q)} T\end{aligned}\tag{16}$$

where $dx = vdt$ in one-dimensional case has been used, and $mv = \alpha\hbar u, \alpha \in \mathbb{R}$, and α is a dimensionless constant, hence, the geometric wave function (14) becomes

$$\Gamma(u, T, w^{(q)}) = u^{-1/2} e^{-\sqrt{-1}w^{(q)}T}$$

where $\alpha = -1$ is taken. Actually, let's take the geometric wave equation (13) to another familiar form like

$$\sqrt{-1}\hbar\hat{w}^{(cl)}\psi = \hat{H}^{(\text{Im})}(\hat{w}^{(cl)})\psi = \frac{\hbar^2}{2m}\left(2u\frac{d\psi}{dx} + \psi\frac{du}{dx}\right)\tag{17}$$

which holds as a first order differential equation which can be much easier to obtain its solution seen from (14). where we denote $E^{(\text{Im})}(\hat{w}^{(cl)}) = \hat{H}^{(\text{Im})}(\hat{w}^{(cl)})$. Notice that it's the same as the Schrödinger equation in form, but its formulation is more easier than Schrödinger equation. In order to show this extremely high similarity, we organize two equations in one dimensional form together.

Schrödinger equation

$$\sqrt{-1}\hbar\partial_t\varphi = \hat{H}^{(cl)}\varphi$$

where $\hat{H}^{(cl)} = -\frac{\hbar^2}{2m}\frac{d^2}{dx^2} + V(x)$ is the classical Hamiltonian operator.

Geometric wave equation

$$\sqrt{-1}\hbar\hat{w}^{(cl)}\psi = \hat{H}^{(\text{Im})}(\hat{w}^{(cl)})\psi$$

where $\hat{H}^{(\text{Im})}(\hat{w}^{(cl)}) = \frac{\hbar^2}{2m}\left(2u\frac{d}{dx} + \frac{du}{dx}\right)$ is the geometric Hamiltonian operator.

Schrödinger equation is a second order differential equation too difficult to get its solution. Obviously, these two equations above are parallel to each other and independent to each other, but it's also connective, furthermore, the geometric wave equation is much easier to get the solution directly expressed as (14).

As a consequence of the G-dynamics, once the Schrödinger equation is given, there always a geometric wave equation follows. In another word, both Schrödinger equation and geometric wave equation is adjoint relation each other.

We have obtained coordinates derivative of the geometric scalar function s , in another aspect, if we take $\hat{H}^{(cl)} = \sqrt{-1}\hbar\partial_t$ which is associated with the partial time derivative to the geometric Hamiltonian operator $\hat{H}^{(Im)} = [s, \hat{H}]_{QPB}$ to see how the geometric scalar function evolves as time goes,

$$\begin{aligned}\hat{H}^{(Im)}(\hat{w}^{(cl)})\psi &= [s, \hat{H}^{(cl)}]_{QPB}\psi = [s, \sqrt{-1}\hbar\partial_t]_{QPB}\psi \\ &= \sqrt{-1}\hbar[s, \partial_t]_{QPB}\psi \\ &= -\psi\sqrt{-1}\hbar\partial_t s\end{aligned}\quad (18)$$

Compare with the geometric wave equation, it generates

$$-\psi\sqrt{-1}\hbar\partial_t s = \sqrt{-1}\hbar\hat{w}^{(cl)}\psi = \hat{H}^{(Im)}(\hat{w}^{(cl)})\psi = \frac{\hbar^2}{2m}\hat{Q}\psi$$

Hence, it leads to the geometric frequency that is given by $w^{(q)} = -\partial_t s$, this gives the time evolution of geometric scalar function s , especially, it leads us to figure the specific geometric frequency out once we choose a proper geometric scalar function s .

$$\partial_t s = \frac{\sqrt{-1}\hbar}{2m\psi}\hat{Q}\psi = -b_c\left(2u\frac{d\ln\psi}{dx} + \frac{du}{dx}\right)$$

It also gets the solution given by

$$\begin{aligned}\psi &= u^{-1/2}\exp\left(-\sqrt{-1}\int\frac{m}{\hbar}\frac{\partial_t s}{u}dx\right) = u^{-1/2}\exp\left(\sqrt{-1}\int w^{(q)}dt\right) \\ &= u^{-1/2}\exp\left(\sqrt{-1}w^{(q)}T\right)\end{aligned}$$

This confirms the specific formula of the geometric frequency given by the partial time derivative of the scalar function s .

Now, we consider the geometrinetic energy operator on the function $u^{-1/2}$, based on identity (15), the geometrinetic energy operator onto it leads to the result

$$\begin{aligned}\hat{T}^{(ri)}u^{-1/2} &= -\frac{\hbar^2}{2m}\left(\frac{d^2}{dx^2} + u^2\right)u^{-1/2} - \sqrt{-1}\hbar\hat{w}^{(cl)}u^{-1/2} \\ &= -\frac{\hbar^2}{2m}\left(\frac{d^2u^{-1/2}}{dx^2} + u^{3/2}\right) \\ &= \frac{\hbar^2}{4m}u^{-3/2}\left(\frac{d^2u}{dx^2} - 3\frac{d\ln u^{1/2}}{dx}\frac{du}{dx} - 2u^3\right)\end{aligned}$$

Hence, $\hat{T}^{(ri)}u^{-1/2} = T^{(ri)}u^{-1/2}$, where energy eigenvalue is

$$T^{(ri)} = \frac{\hbar^2}{2m} \left(\frac{1}{2u} \frac{d^2u}{dx^2} - 3 \left(\frac{d \ln u^{1/2}}{dx} \right)^2 - u^2 \right)$$

in terms of the eigenfunction $u^{-1/2}$.

What's more, consider the polar form for the wave function $\varphi = A^{(b)} \exp(\sqrt{-1}S/\hbar)$ with real-valued functions $A^{(b)}$ and S , where $A^{(b)}$ is the amplitude (absolute value) of the wave function φ , and $S/\hbar$ its phase, we use quantum potential [15]

$$Q^{(cl)} = -\frac{\hbar^2}{2m} \frac{\nabla^2 A^{(b)}}{A^{(b)}}.$$

to rewrite the geometrinetic energy operator in one dimensional case, for this reason, we have amplitude $A^{(b)} = u^{-1/2}$ for the geometric wave equation (14) $\Gamma(u, w^{(g)})$, then by using the formula of the quantum potential $Q^{(cl)} = -\frac{\hbar^2}{2m} \frac{d^2 A^{(b)}}{A^{(b)} dx^2}$ in one dimensional case, it gives

$$Q^{(cl)} = -\frac{\hbar^2}{2m} u^{1/2} \frac{d^2 u^{-1/2}}{dx^2} = \frac{\hbar^2}{2m} \left(\frac{1}{2u} \frac{d^2 u}{dx^2} - 3 \left(\frac{d \ln u^{1/2}}{dx} \right)^2 \right)$$

As a consequence, the geometrinetic energy operator is given by

$$T^{(ri)} = Q^{(cl)} - \frac{\hbar^2}{2m} u^2$$

Then the geometric quantum potential ² is

$$\begin{aligned} Q^{(s)} &= \frac{\hat{E}^{(w)} A^{(b)}}{A^{(b)}} - \frac{\hbar^2}{2m} u^2 = \frac{\hat{E}^{(w)} u^{-1/2}}{u^{-1/2}} - \frac{\hbar^2}{2m} u^2 \\ &= Q^{(cl)} - \frac{\hbar^2}{2m} u^2 = T^{(ri)} \end{aligned}$$

where

$$\hat{E}^{(w)} = -\frac{\hbar^2}{2m} \frac{d^2}{dx^2} - \sqrt{-1} \hbar \hat{w}^{(cl)}$$

is motor operator, and (15) has been used, the potenergy $E^{(wg)} = -\sqrt{-1} \hbar \hat{w}^{(cl)} A^{(b)} / A^{(b)}$ here vanishes.

We consider (6) which is similar to

$$\left(\hat{T}^{(ri)} - \hat{T}^{*(ri)} \right) / (2\hbar) = -\sqrt{-1} \hat{w}^{(cl)}$$

then we get

$$\frac{\left(\hat{H}^{*(gr)} - \hat{H}^{(gr)} \right) \psi}{2\hbar \psi} = -\sqrt{-1} \frac{\hat{w}^{(cl)} \psi}{\psi} = -\sqrt{-1} w^{(g)}$$

As we can analyze, this is unique formula associated with the spatial energy by introducing the geometric function or the scalar potential function s , not matter energy, hence, it confirms the special status of the G-dynamics $\hat{w}^{(cl)}$. As mentioned previously, the parameters $u, w^{(g)}$ are used for describing the properties of the quantum space or the quantum environment.

²[See [15] for more details]

4.1 Mass-energy formula by quantum method

This section, we will show the quantum kinetic energy expression in relativity. Now let's compute the work given by follows

$$\begin{aligned} W &= \int F \cdot dx = \hbar \int \frac{du}{dt} \cdot v dt = \hbar \int v du \\ &= \alpha \frac{\hbar^2}{m} \int u du = \alpha \frac{\hbar^2}{2m} u^2 + C \\ &= \frac{\alpha}{2} E^{(s)} + C \end{aligned}$$

where C is a constant, we can find that $W = \alpha \frac{\hbar^2}{2m} u^2 + C$ is kept the same pattern as the kinetic energy. For $\alpha = 1$ and initial condition, we obtain

$$W = \frac{\hbar^2}{2m} u^2 - \frac{\hbar^2}{2m} u_0^2$$

where as we mentioned, the function u is a continuous function in terms of the coordinates, obviously, it plays a role like the velocity. For this reason, $T^{(ge)}(u) = \frac{\hbar^2}{2m} u^2$ can be given a name—geometric kinetic energy.

If we consider the relativistic mass given by

$$m = m_0 \gamma = \frac{m_0}{\sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}}}$$

Then it leads to the result

$$v = \alpha \frac{\hbar u}{m_0} \sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}} \Rightarrow v^2 = \frac{c^2}{1 + \frac{m_0^2 c^2}{\hbar^2 u^2}}$$

where $\delta = \frac{m_0^2 c^2}{\hbar^2}$, $\alpha^2 = 1$, in this way, we repeat the same way for getting the work in one dimensional case, as we can see, this transformation connects the velocity to the line curvature, we will derive the mass-energy formula by using the quantum method, it reveals our way of proving the RH, somehow, thusly, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} W &= \int F \cdot dx = \hbar \int v du = \hbar c \int \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 + \frac{m_0^2 c^2}{\hbar^2 u^2}}} du \\ &= \hbar c \int \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 + \delta \frac{1}{u^2}}} du \\ &= \hbar c \int \frac{u}{\sqrt{u^2 + \delta}} du \\ &= \frac{1}{2} \hbar c \int \frac{1}{\sqrt{u^2 + \delta}} du^2 \\ &= \hbar c (u^2 + \delta)^{1/2} + C_2 \\ &= \hbar c \left(u^2 + \frac{m_0^2 c^2}{\hbar^2} \right)^{1/2} + C_2 \end{aligned}$$

Taking advantage of the mass equation, we can simplify above relativistic power to a mass-energy formula,

$$W = \hbar c \left(u^2 + \frac{m_0^2 c^2}{\hbar^2} \right)^{1/2} + C_2 = mc^2 + C_2$$

based on the initial condition, $C_2 = -m_0 c^2$, then $W = mc^2 - m_0 c^2$, the above formula is the kinetic energy expression in relativity. This way to get the mass-energy formula indicates the reasonable connection between the classical mechanics and quantum mechanics.

4.1.1 Geometric wave function in relativistic case

If we reconsider the (16) in relativistic mass, then by using the formula $v^2 = \frac{c^2}{1 + \frac{\delta}{u^2}}$, we can directly deduce the result as follows

$$\begin{aligned} \int \frac{m w^{(q)}}{\hbar u} dx &= \int \frac{m_0}{\hbar u \sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}}} w^{(q)} dx = \frac{m_0}{\hbar} w^{(q)} \int \frac{dt}{u \sqrt{\frac{1}{v^2} - \frac{1}{c^2}}} \\ &= \frac{m_0 w^{(q)}}{\hbar} \int \frac{dt}{u \sqrt{\frac{\delta}{c^2 u^2}}} \\ &= w^{(q)} \int dt = w^{(q)} T \end{aligned}$$

where T is the orbit period. As a consequence, the (14) turns to a simple form

$$\Gamma(u, T, w^{(q)}) = u^{-1/2} \exp(\sqrt{-1} w^{(q)} T)$$

where $w^{(q)}$ is the geometric frequency corresponding to what kind of period T , on the other hand, this inspires us a way to solve the HP conjecture and BK conjecture, in particular, the geometric frequency creates the energy spectrum $E^{(q)} = \hbar w^{(q)}$. Therefore, we take the discrete procedure to essentially simplify the above formula with three variables $u, T, w^{(q)}$:

$$\Gamma_n(w^{(q)}) = \Gamma(n, T_n, w^{(q)}) = n^{-1/2 + \sqrt{-1} w^{(q)}}$$

where $T_n = \ln n$, it means that the discrete period corresponds to the discrete geometric frequency, $\Gamma_n(w^{(q)})$ demonstrates discrete geometric frequency all lie on fixed horizontal ordinate $1/2$ on the complex plain. Summing up all the integer to infinity, it yields the same result as the non-trivial zeros of the Riemann zeta function hold.

$$\begin{aligned} \xi(w^{(q)}) &= \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \Gamma_n(w^{(q)}) = \zeta\left(1/2 - \sqrt{-1} w^{(q)}\right) \\ &= \zeta\left(1/2 - \sqrt{-1} \frac{E^{(q)}}{\hbar}\right) = 0 \end{aligned}$$

This is exactly what Berry and Keating wants the result. So, the imaginary parts, λ of the non-trivial zeros $1/2 + \sqrt{-1}\lambda$ of the Riemann zeta function corresponded to eigenvalues $w^{(q)}$ of an unbounded self-adjoint operator $\hat{w}^{(cl)}$, where $\hat{w}^{(cl)}\psi = w^{(q)}\psi$, note that identity (15) verifies all eigenvalues $w^{(q)}$ of self-adjoint operator $\hat{w}^{(cl)}$ are on the critical line $1/2$. In this way, we prove the HP conjecture, then the RH follows as a corollary. The Riemann zeros are related to the eigenvalues $w^{(q)}$ (vibration geometric frequencies, or quantum energies) of geometric wave equation.

4.2 G-dynamics $\hat{w}^{(cl)}$ on classical momentum operator

Actually, we know that classical momentum operator in one dimensional case is given by $\hat{p}^{(cl)} = -\sqrt{-1}\hbar\frac{d}{dx}$, then let $\hat{v}^{(cl)} = \frac{\hat{p}^{(cl)}}{m} = -\frac{\sqrt{-1}\hbar}{m}\frac{d}{dx}$ be denoted as a classical velocity operator for simple discussion. In the beginning, we start with the below identities

$$\begin{aligned}\hat{v}^{(cl)}_s &= \frac{\hat{p}^{(cl)}_s}{m} = -\frac{\sqrt{-1}\hbar u}{m} = \sqrt{-1}v^{(s)} \\ \hat{v}^{(cl)}_x &= \frac{\hat{p}^{(cl)}_x}{m} = -\frac{\sqrt{-1}\hbar}{m} \\ \hat{v}^{(cl)}_u &= \frac{\hat{p}^{(cl)}_u}{m} = -\frac{\sqrt{-1}\hbar}{m}\frac{du}{dx} \\ u\hat{v}^{(cl)} &= \frac{u\hat{p}^{(cl)}}{m} = -\frac{\sqrt{-1}\hbar}{m}u\frac{d}{dx}\end{aligned}$$

By using these notions, we can simplify the formula of the G-dynamics $\hat{w}^{(cl)}$ (12) to a more compact form,

$$\boxed{\hat{w}^{(cl)} = b_c\hat{Q} = u\hat{v}^{(cl)} + \frac{1}{2}\hat{v}^{(cl)}_u}$$

Clearly, this formula expresses a better structure to help us understand the G-dynamics, in particular, this kind of formula is highly similar to the Hamiltonian operator (10), but the different thing is that we deduce this equation by QCPB theory, in other words, it's not constructed on purpose, but by rational logic derivation. It also can be expressed as

$$\hat{w}^{(cl)} = \frac{u\hat{p}^{(cl)}}{m} + \frac{\hat{p}^{(cl)}_u}{2m} = \frac{1}{m}\left(u\hat{p}^{(cl)} + \frac{\hat{p}^{(cl)}_u}{2}\right)$$

by taking advantage of the equality $\hat{p}^{(cl)} = m\hat{v}^{(cl)}$. By the way, the imaginary geomen-ergy is given by

$$H^{(Im)}\left(\hat{w}^{(cl)}\right) = \sqrt{-1}\hbar\hat{w}^{(cl)} = \sqrt{-1}\hbar u\hat{v}^{(cl)} + \frac{\sqrt{-1}}{2}\hbar\hat{v}^{(cl)}_u$$

Let us consider the eigenvalue equation

$$\begin{aligned}\hat{v}^{(cl)}\eta &= -\frac{\sqrt{-1}\hbar}{m}\frac{d\eta}{dx} = v\eta \\ d\ln\eta &= \sqrt{-1}\frac{mv}{\hbar}dx = \sqrt{-1}\frac{mv}{\hbar u}ds = \sqrt{-1}\alpha ds\end{aligned}$$

Then by simple calculation, we obtain the eigenfunction $\eta = \eta_0 e^{\sqrt{-1}\alpha s}$. In fact, if we let $\tilde{w} = \hat{v}^{(cl)}u$, then

$$\begin{aligned}\hat{w}^{(cl)} &= u\hat{v}^{(cl)} + \frac{1}{2}\hat{v}^{(cl)}u = u\hat{v}^{(cl)} + \frac{1}{2}\tilde{w} \\ &= \tilde{w} \left(\frac{u}{\tilde{w}}\hat{v}^{(cl)} + \frac{1}{2} \right)\end{aligned}$$

where $\hat{v}^{(cl)} = -\frac{\sqrt{-1}\hbar}{m} \frac{d}{dx}$, at the same time, we have

$$\hat{w}^{(cl)}/u = \hat{v}^{(cl)} \left(\mathbb{I} - \ln u^{-1/2} \right)$$

where $\mathbb{I}$ is unit operator.

4.3 Gutzwillers trace formula

Periodic-orbit theory gives a recipe for computing spectra from the periodic orbits of a system. Gutzwiller's trace formula of 1971 expresses the density of states of a quantum mechanical system approximately as a sum over all periodic classical orbits.

Gutzwiller gave a trace formula in the setting of quantum chaos which relates the classical and quantum mechanical pictures. Given a chaotic (classical) dynamical system, there will exist a dense set of periodic orbits, and one side of the trace formula will be a sum over the lengths of these orbits. On the other side will be a sum over the eigenvalues of the Hamiltonian in the quantum mechanical analog of the given classical dynamical system. Quantum chaos is the subject devoted to the study of quantum systems corresponding to classically chaotic systems. The Berry-Keating conjecture shed light further into the Riemann dynamics, sketching some of the properties of the dynamical system behind the Riemann hypothesis.

For a better background understanding, we will offer some more knowledge about Gutzwiller's trace formula. The total trace of the Green function must thus be divided into two parts [See [17] for more derivations]

$$\text{Tr } G(E) = \text{Tr } G_0(E) + \sum_j \text{Tr } G_j^{\text{long}}(q, q', E)$$

where the first term represents zero length contributions

$$\text{Tr } G_0(E) = \int d^d q \lim_{q' \rightarrow q} G^{\text{short}}(q, q', E)$$

and the second term long trajectory contributions

$$\begin{aligned}\text{Tr } G_j^{\text{long}}(q, q', E) &= \int d^d q G_j^{\text{long}}(q, q, E) \\ &= \int d^d q \frac{|\det D_{\perp, j}(q, q, E)|^{\frac{1}{2}} e^{\sqrt{-1}S_j(q, q, E)/\hbar - \sqrt{-1}\pi\mu_j(q, q, E)/2}}{\sqrt{-1}\hbar(2\pi\hbar\sqrt{-1})^{(d-1)/2} |\dot{q}|}\end{aligned}$$

where μ_j is an integer characteristic of the orbit called Maslov index. Then it's simplified as

$$\text{Tr } G_j^{\text{long}}(q, q', E) = \oint \frac{dq_{\parallel}}{\dot{q}_{\parallel}} \frac{e^{\sqrt{-1}S_j(E)/\hbar - \sqrt{-1}\pi\mu_j(E)/2}}{\sqrt{-1}\hbar |\det(\mathbb{I} - \mathbf{J}_j)|^{1/2}}$$

with $\mathbb{I}$ being the unit matrix. The last integration is carried out over one period giving that

$$\oint \frac{dq_{\parallel}}{\dot{q}_{\parallel}} = \oint dt = T_j$$

The sum over all closed orbits will contain also orbits going several revolutions. These repeated revolutions can be dealt with by just summing over all prime closed orbits, and for every prime orbit sum over the number of revolutions, r , where $S \rightarrow rS, \mu \rightarrow r\mu$ and $\mathbf{J} \rightarrow \mathbf{J}^r$. Finally the Gutzwiller Trace Formula is obtained,

$$\text{Tr } G(q, q', E) = \text{Tr } G_0 + \frac{1}{\sqrt{-1}\hbar} \sum_{j,r} T_r \frac{1}{|\det(\mathbb{I} - \mathbf{J}_j^r)|^{1/2}} e^{\sqrt{-1}rS_j(E)/\hbar - \sqrt{-1}\pi r\mu_j(E)/2}$$

expressing the relation between the quantum mechanical energy levels of the system and its purely classical stable orbits. [17]

The result about a derivation of the trace formula given by [18] is

$$\text{Tr } G(E) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{-1}\hbar} \int dq \sum_k \frac{B_{j(k)}}{|\dot{q}_k|} \exp(\sqrt{-1}S_{j(k)}/\hbar - \sqrt{-1}\mu_k\pi/2)$$

where k labels intersections of $\Sigma(qE)$ by periodic orbits $z_{j(k)}(t)$. Adding together contributions k corresponding to a single periodic orbit $z_j(t)$, we obtain the primitive period

$$T_j = \oint dq/|\dot{q}_j|$$

where T_j is the primitive period of the orbit, i.e. the time taken for a single iteration, and the final result follows

$$\text{Tr } G(E) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{-1}\hbar} \sum_j T_j B_j \exp(\sqrt{-1}S_j/\hbar - \sqrt{-1}\mu_j\pi/2)$$

where the j sum is taken over distinct periodic orbits and their repetitions, and B_j depends only on the Liapunov exponents of the orbit, and therefore like the action is a canonical invariant. [See [18] for more derivations].

Gutzwiller's trace formula provides a semiclassical expansion for the quantum mechanical density of states. Since this quantity a priori requires a Hamiltonian with a discrete spectrum, [see [13] for more details]

$$d(E) = \sum_n \delta(E - E_n)$$

of a given quantum system and the periodic orbits of the underlying classical dynamics:

$$d(E) \sim \bar{d}(E) + \frac{1}{\pi\hbar} \text{Re} \sum_{\mathbf{p}} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{T_{\mathbf{p}}}{|\det(M_{\mathbf{p}}^n - I)|^{1/2}} \exp\left(\frac{\sqrt{-1}}{\hbar} n S_{\mathbf{p}}\right)$$

where $\bar{d}$ is the mean density; $\mathbf{p}$ is the primes that labels primitive orbits and n their repetitions; the $\mathbf{p}$ sum is taken over periodic orbits with energy E , $T_{\mathbf{p}}$ is the period of the $\mathbf{p}$ -th orbit, it shows that the classical system corresponding to Riemann system has a l

closed orbit whose period is equal to the prime logarithm $T_{\mathbf{p}}$, and $S_{\mathbf{p}}$ its action (defined here to include the Maslov index), and $M_{\mathbf{p}}$ the monodromy matrix that describes the flow linearized in its vicinity. $|\det(M_{\mathbf{p}}^n - I)|^{-1/2}$ depends only on the Liapunov exponents of the orbit, and therefore like the action is a canonical invariant. The periodic orbit theory is able to reproduce a discrete spectrum which, on scales of the order of the mean level separation, represents a good approximation to the true quantum energy levels in systems whose classical dynamics is integrable, chaotic, or mixed; and that in principle the method can be extended to any desired order of accuracy.

4.3.1 Counting functions and periodic orbits

The basis of the analogy is a formal similarity between representations for the fluctuations of the counting functions for the Riemann zeros λ_n and for vibration frequencies associated with a system whose rays are chaotic. For the λ_n , the counting function $N : \{\lambda \in \mathbb{R} | \lambda > 0\} \rightarrow \mathbb{Q}$ is defined for $\lambda > 0$ as

$$N(\lambda) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \theta(\lambda - \lambda_n)$$

where $\theta : \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{Q}$ is the Heaviside step function, also known as the unit step function, given by

$$\theta(x) = \begin{cases} 0, & x < 0 \\ 1/2, & x = 0 \\ 1, & x > 0 \end{cases}$$

and λ_n is the n -th zero of the Riemann zeta function above the real line.

$$N(\lambda) = 1 - \frac{\lambda}{2\pi} \ln \pi + \frac{1}{\pi} \arg \left(\Gamma \left(\frac{1}{4} + \sqrt{-1} \frac{\lambda}{2} \right) \right) + \frac{1}{\pi} \arg \left(\zeta \left(\frac{1}{2} + \sqrt{-1} \lambda \right) \right)$$

where

$$\arg \left(\Gamma \left(\frac{1}{4} + \sqrt{-1} \frac{\lambda}{2} \right) \right) = \frac{\lambda}{2} \ln \left(\frac{\lambda}{2} \right) - \frac{\lambda}{2} - \frac{\pi}{8} + O \left(\frac{1}{\lambda} \right)$$

As a result,

$$N(\lambda) = \frac{\lambda}{2\pi} \ln \left(\frac{\lambda}{2\pi} \right) - \frac{\lambda}{2\pi} + \frac{7}{8} + O \left(\frac{1}{\lambda} \right) + \frac{1}{\pi} \arg \left(\zeta \left(\frac{1}{2} + \sqrt{-1} \lambda \right) \right)$$

Often, this counting function is separated into a smooth part and a fluctuating part

$$N(\lambda) = \langle N(\lambda) \rangle + N_{fl}(\lambda)$$

where

$$\langle N(\lambda) \rangle = \frac{\lambda}{2\pi} \ln \left(\frac{\lambda}{2\pi} \right) - \frac{\lambda}{2\pi} + \frac{7}{8} + O \left(\frac{1}{\lambda} \right)$$

is the smooth part and

$$N_{fl}(\lambda) = \frac{1}{\pi} \arg \zeta \left(\frac{1}{2} + \sqrt{-1} \lambda \right) = \frac{1}{\pi} \lim_{\varepsilon \rightarrow 0} \text{Im} \ln \zeta \left(\frac{1}{2} + \sqrt{-1} \lambda + \varepsilon \right)$$

is the fluctuating part. Then the fluctuating part becomes

$$\begin{aligned}
N_{\text{fl}}(\lambda) &= \frac{1}{\pi} \arg \left(\prod_{\mathbf{p} \in \mathbb{P}} \frac{1}{1 - \mathbf{p}^{-\frac{1}{2} - \sqrt{-1}\lambda}} \right) = -\frac{1}{\pi} \text{Im} \sum_{\mathbf{p} \in \mathbb{P}} \ln \left(1 - \mathbf{p}^{-\frac{1}{2} - \sqrt{-1}\lambda} \right) \\
&= -\frac{1}{\pi} \sum_{\mathbf{p} \in \mathbb{P}} \text{Im} \left(\ln \left(1 - e^{(-\frac{1}{2} - \sqrt{-1}\lambda) \ln \mathbf{p}} \right) \right) \\
&= -\frac{1}{\pi} \sum_{\mathbf{p} \in \mathbb{P}} \text{Im} \left(\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^{n+1}}{n} \left(-e^{(-\frac{1}{2} - \sqrt{-1}\lambda) \ln \mathbf{p}} \right)^n \right) \\
&= -\frac{1}{\pi} \sum_{\mathbf{p} \in \mathbb{P}} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^{2n+1} e^{-\frac{1}{2}n \ln \mathbf{p}}}{n} \text{Im} \left(-e^{-\sqrt{-1}n\lambda \ln \mathbf{p}} \right) \\
&= -\frac{1}{\pi} \sum_{\mathbf{p} \in \mathbb{P}} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{-e^{-\frac{1}{2}n \ln \mathbf{p}}}{n} \sin(-n\lambda \ln \mathbf{p})
\end{aligned}$$

to conclude with

$$\begin{aligned}
N_{\text{fl}}(\lambda) &= -\frac{1}{\pi} \text{Im} \sum_{\mathbf{p}} \ln \left\{ 1 - \frac{\exp(-\sqrt{-1}\lambda \ln \mathbf{p})}{\sqrt{\mathbf{p}}} \right\} \\
&= -\frac{1}{\pi} \sum_{\mathbf{p} \in \mathbb{P}} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{\exp(-\frac{1}{2}n \ln \mathbf{p})}{n} \sin\{\lambda n \ln \mathbf{p}\}
\end{aligned}$$

This formula gives the fluctuations as a series of oscillatory contributions, each labelled by a prime $\mathbf{p}$ and an integer n , corresponding to the prime power $\mathbf{p}^m$.

	Generic chaotic system	Riemann zeta function
periodic orbit labels	integers	primes
dimensionless action	$S_{\mathbf{p}}/\hbar$	$T \ln \mathbf{p}$
period of the orbit	$T_{\mathbf{p}}$	$\ln \mathbf{p}$
stability factor	$\det(M_{\mathbf{p}}^n - I)$	$\mathbf{p}^r$
Maslov index	$\mu_{\mathbf{p}}$	2
asymptotic limit	$\hbar \rightarrow 0$	$T_{\mathbf{p}} \rightarrow \infty$

Table 1: The correspondence between the chaotic system corresponding to the Riemann zeta function

where stability factor and Maslov index in the above table are depending on how one maps the oscillatory part of the zeta zeros density onto Gutzwiller's trace formula.

In 1985, Berry, M V has discussed the Riemann zeta function in the paper [14], Periodic orbit theory gives the semiclassical spectral density as

$$d(E) = \langle d(E) \rangle + d_{\text{osc}}(E)$$

where $d_{\text{osc}}(E)$ is a sum over classical periodic orbits, each of which contributes an oscillatory function and whose combined effect is to produce, the oscillatory contribution

in this equation is

$$d_{\text{osc}}(E) = \frac{1}{\hbar^{\mu+1}} \sum_j A_j(E) \exp\{\sqrt{-1}S_j(E)/\hbar\} \quad (19)$$

he assumed that $z \equiv \frac{1}{2} + \sqrt{-1}E$, and then let $\zeta(\frac{1}{2} - \sqrt{-1}E) \equiv \xi(E)$, subsequently, it has

$$\ln \xi(E) = - \sum_{\mathbf{p}} \ln \left(1 - \exp\{\sqrt{-1}E \ln \mathbf{p}\} / \mathbf{p}^{\frac{1}{2}} \right)$$

Assuming the Riemann hypothesis, and noting that $\ln \xi$ vanishes as $\text{Im } E \rightarrow +\infty$ we see that this function jumps by $-\sqrt{-1}\pi$ as each Riemann zero $E = E_n$ is traversed from above, so that the oscillatory part of the spectral staircase is

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{N}_{\text{osc}}(E) &= -\pi^{-1} \lim_{(\varepsilon \rightarrow 0)} \text{Im} \ln \xi(E + \sqrt{-1}\varepsilon) \\ &= -\frac{1}{\pi} \text{Im} \sum_{\mathbf{p}} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{\exp\{\sqrt{-1}n \ln \mathbf{p}\}}{n \mathbf{p}^{\frac{1}{2}n}} \end{aligned}$$

where the index $\mathbf{p}$ labels the primitive periodic orbits (the smallest periodic orbits of a given set of initial conditions) and the index n labels their repetitions.

The oscillatory part of the spectral density is therefore

$$d_{\text{osc}}(E) = -\frac{1}{\pi} \sum_{\mathbf{p}} \frac{\ln \mathbf{p} \left[\cos(E \ln \mathbf{p}) - \mathbf{p}^{-\frac{1}{2}} \right]}{1 - 2 \cos(E \ln \mathbf{p}) / \mathbf{p}^{\frac{1}{2}} - \mathbf{p}^{-1}}$$

Or

$$d_{\text{osc}}(E) = -\frac{1}{2\pi} \sum_{\mathbf{p}} \sum_{n=-\infty}^{\infty} \ln \mathbf{p} \exp\{-|n| \ln \mathbf{p} / 2\} \exp\{\sqrt{-1}En \ln \mathbf{p}\} \quad (20)$$

In the form (20) the analogy with (19) the periodic orbit formula is clear: each primitive orbit corresponds to a prime $\mathbf{p}$ and is traversed n times; the action is $S_{n,\mathbf{p}} = En \ln \mathbf{p}$. If E is regarded as the energy, the period is $T_{n,\mathbf{p}} = dS_{n,\mathbf{p}}/dE = nT_{\mathbf{p}}$ and the amplitude is $A_{n,\mathbf{p}} = -(\ln \mathbf{p} \exp\{-|n| \ln \mathbf{p} / 2\}) / 2\pi$, where discrete period $T_{\mathbf{p}} = \ln \mathbf{p}$. Hence, we can see that there exists discrete period $T_{\mathbf{p}} = \ln \mathbf{p}$ that is the primitive period of the $\mathbf{p}$ -th orbit, for general case, it's replaced by $T_n = \ln n$.

Let's review fundamental theorem of arithmetic, the fundamental theorem of arithmetic states that every integer greater than either is a prime number itself or can be represented as the product of prime numbers and that, moreover, this representation is unique, up to the order of the factors. Every positive integer $n > 1$ can be represented in exactly one way as a product of prime powers:

$$n = \mathbf{p}_1^{n_1} \mathbf{p}_2^{n_2} \cdots \mathbf{p}_j^{n_j} = \prod_{i=1}^j \mathbf{p}_i^{n_i}$$

where $\mathbf{p}_1 < \mathbf{p}_2 < \cdots < \mathbf{p}_j$ are primes and the n_i are positive integers which represents the number of repetitions of the orbit $\mathbf{p}$. As a result, combining the discrete periodic orbit $T_{\mathbf{p}} = \ln \mathbf{p}$, we obtain the sum of orbit period expressed as

$$T_n = \ln n = \ln \left(\prod_{i=1}^j \mathbf{p}_i^{n_i} \right) = \sum_{i=1}^j n_i \ln \mathbf{p}_i = \sum_{i=1}^j n_i T_{\mathbf{p}_i} \quad (21)$$

Clearly, T_n is the linear sum of the discrete periodic orbit $T_{\mathbf{p}_i} = \ln \mathbf{p}_i$. In particular, if $n_i = 1$ are given for a special case, namely, $n = \prod_{i=1}^j \mathbf{p}_i$, then

$$T_n = \ln n = \ln \left(\prod_{i=1}^j \mathbf{p}_i \right) = \sum_{i=1}^j \ln \mathbf{p}_i = \sum_{i=1}^j T_{\mathbf{p}_i}$$

Consequently, this expresses the existence of discrete period and is closely linked to the primes, that's why the heights λ_n are frequencies of some vibrating system, subsequently, discrete period T_n will provide one part for the proof of the RH.

4.4 The G-dynamics on time derivative

In fact, the formula of the G-dynamics can be replaced by another simple form

$$\hat{w}^{(cl)} = b_c \frac{2u}{v} \left(\frac{d}{dt} + \frac{d \ln u^{1/2}}{dt} \right) = -\sqrt{-1}\alpha \left(\frac{d}{dt} + \frac{d \ln u^{1/2}}{dt} \right)$$

associated with the time derivative, a time derivative is a derivative of a function with respect to time, usually interpreted as the rate of change of the value of the function, it is clear to see that the G-dynamics in this form is much easier than before, it becomes effectively to understand, in particular, the solution can be simply obtained by easy computation. As a result, it turns out that the curvature operator then becomes

$$\hat{Q} = \frac{2u}{v} \left(\frac{d}{dt} + \frac{d \ln u^{1/2}}{dt} \right) \quad (22)$$

At the same time, it also turns to the form given by $\hat{w}^{(cl)} = 2b_c u \left(\frac{d}{dx} + \frac{d \ln u^{1/2}}{dx} \right)$. This expression is very similar to above simple formula. When $\alpha = 1$ is chosen, then it can be simplified as

$$\hat{w}^{(cl)} = -\sqrt{-1} \left(\frac{d}{dt} + \frac{d \ln u^{1/2}}{dt} \right) \quad (23)$$

When we consider the relativistic condition of the G-dynamics $\hat{w}^{(cl)}$, it becomes

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{w}^{(cl)} &= -\frac{\sqrt{-1}\hbar}{2m_0} \sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}} \hat{Q} = -\frac{\sqrt{-1}\hbar}{2m_0} \sqrt{1 - \frac{1}{1 + \frac{\delta}{u^2}}} \hat{Q} \\ &= -\frac{\sqrt{-1}\hbar}{2m_0} \sqrt{\frac{\delta}{u^2 + \delta}} \hat{Q} \\ &= -\frac{\sqrt{-1}\hbar}{2m_0} \delta^{1/2} \frac{v}{uc} \hat{Q} \\ &= -\frac{\sqrt{-1}v}{2u} \hat{Q} \end{aligned}$$

where $\delta^{1/2} = m_0 c / \hbar$, subsequently, we insert the curvature operator (22) to above relativistic expression, then it goes back to the expression (23). The G-dynamics $\hat{w}^{(cl)}$ also can be expressed as

$$\sqrt{-1}\hat{w}^{(cl)} = \frac{d}{dt} + \frac{d \ln u^{1/2}}{dt}$$

as a result, the solution of the eigenvalue equation certainly exists

$$\sqrt{-1}\hat{w}^{(cl)}\psi = \frac{d\psi}{dt} + \psi\frac{d\ln u^{1/2}}{dt} = \sqrt{-1}w^{(q)}\psi \quad (24)$$

and gives rise to the unique solution

$$\psi = C_0u^{-1/2}\exp\left(\sqrt{-1}w^{(q)}t\right) = C_0u^{-1/2}e^{\sqrt{-1}\frac{E^{(q)}}{\hbar}t} \quad (25)$$

where $\hat{w}^{(cl)}u^{-1/2} \equiv 0$ and $E^{(q)} = \hbar w^{(q)}$ is the definite energy, in quantum mechanics, there exists a state with completely determined energy, here we denote period $T = t = \oint dt$ in a general form t corresponding to the geometric frequency $w^{(q)}$. As we know, a quantum mechanical system is completely described by its wave function, for this reason, the geometric wave function (25) as a unique solution that describes a unique quantum mechanical system given by the G-dynamics. Obviously, such existence of this unique quantum mechanical system is what we call mysterious Riemann system.

4.4.1 Geometric frequency spectrum on critical line 1/2

In this section, the quantization of the geometric wave function (25) is given, we will see how the discretization of geometric wave function (25) means and induces the geometric frequency spectrum. Transparently, the general solution is the same as we obtained before. The main contribution of the geometric wave function may be rewritten in the form

$$\Gamma\left(u, t, w^{(q)}\right) = u^{-1/2}e^{\sqrt{-1}w^{(q)}t} = u^{-1/2}e^{\sqrt{-1}\frac{E^{(q)}}{\hbar}t} \quad (26)$$

which is also the solution of above eigenvalue equation (24) and is a stationary state wave functions, clearly, the solution $\Gamma\left(u, t, w^{(q)}\right)$ is unique to explain how the eigenvalue equation exactly means.

We will see how the discrete formula of the geometric wave function (26) shows, hence, we simultaneously take the three parameters $u, t, w^{(q)}$ to be discrete.

$$\Gamma\left(n, t, w^{(q)}\right) = n^{-1/2+\sqrt{-1}w^{(q)}}e^{\sqrt{-1}w^{(q)}(t-T_n)} \quad (27)$$

Actually, (27) clearly shows the discrete essence of the geometric wave function (25), naturally.

$$\Gamma\left(n, t, w^{(q)}\right)e^{\sqrt{-1}w^{(q)}(T_n-t)} = q_n\left(1/2 - \sqrt{-1}w^{(q)}\right)$$

where $z = 1/2 - \sqrt{-1}w^{(q)}$ means all eigenvalues $w^{(q)}$ all lie on fixed abscissa 1/2.

It implies that $u, t, w^{(q)}$ all are discrete form with meanings. Consequently, summing up from 1 to infinity of n , it leads to the result

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty}\Gamma\left(n, t, w^{(q)}\right) &= \sum_{n=1}^{\infty}n^{-1/2+\sqrt{-1}w^{(q)}}n^{\left(\frac{t}{T_n}-1\right)\sqrt{-1}w^{(q)}} \\ &= \sum_{n=1}^{\infty}\Gamma_n\left(w^{(q)}\right)e^{\sqrt{-1}w^{(q)}(t-T_n)} \end{aligned}$$

where $\Gamma_n(w^{(q)}) = q_n(1/2 - \sqrt{-1}w^{(q)})$. As a matter of fact, we can compare (9) with (27) together to see this similarity for both expression

$$\begin{cases} \Gamma(n, t, w^{(q)}) = q_n(1/2 - \sqrt{-1}w^{(q)}) e^{\sqrt{-1}w^{(q)}(t-T_n)} \\ q_n(1/2 + \sqrt{-1}\lambda) = n^{-1/2-\sqrt{-1}\lambda} \end{cases}$$

Or we can write it to a familiar form

$$\Gamma(n, t, -w^{(q)}) = q_n(1/2 + \sqrt{-1}w^{(q)}) e^{\sqrt{-1}w^{(q)}(t-T_n)}$$

Remember here the time $t = T$ is the primitive period of the orbit in terms of the geometric frequency $w^{(q)}$.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\Gamma(n, t, w^{(q)})}{q_n(1/2 + \sqrt{-1}\lambda)} &= \frac{q_n(1/2 - \sqrt{-1}w^{(q)})}{q_n(1/2 + \sqrt{-1}\lambda)} e^{\sqrt{-1}w^{(q)}(t-T_n)} \\ &= n^{\sqrt{-1}(w^{(q)}+\lambda)} e^{\sqrt{-1}w^{(q)}(t-T_n)} \end{aligned}$$

The ratio of conjugate form is

$$\frac{\Gamma^*(n, t, w^{(q)})}{q_n(1/2 + \sqrt{-1}\lambda)} = e^{\sqrt{-1}w^{(q)}(T_n-t)} q_n(1/2 + \sqrt{-1}w^{(q)}) / q_n(1/2 + \sqrt{-1}\lambda)$$

where

$$\Gamma(n, t, -w^{(q)}) = \Gamma^*(n, t, w^{(q)}) = n^{-1/2-\sqrt{-1}w^{(q)}} n^{(1-\frac{t}{T_n})\sqrt{-1}w^{(q)}}$$

According to the results given by Gutzwiller trace formula, there exists a discrete period, the integration is carried out over one period giving that

$$\oint dt = T_n$$

which is the primitive discrete period of the orbit. On the support of the (21), it leads to

$$w^{(q)}T_n = \sum_{i=1}^j n_i w^{(q)} T_{\mathbf{p}_i} = \sum_{i=1}^j n_i \frac{E^{(q)} T_{\mathbf{p}_i}}{\hbar} \quad (28)$$

If we identify the actions of the closed orbits $S_{n_i, \mathbf{p}_i} = n_i S_{\mathbf{p}_i}$ to above, where

$$S_{\mathbf{p}_i} = E^{(q)} T_{\mathbf{p}_i}$$

then in turn, the (28) is simplified as

$$w^{(q)}T_n = \sum_{i=1}^j S_{n_i, \mathbf{p}_i} / \hbar = \sum_{i=1}^j n_i S_{\mathbf{p}_i} / \hbar = S_n / \hbar$$

and each term corresponds to a sum over actions, $S_n = E^{(q)}T_n = \sum_{i=1}^j S_{n_i, \mathbf{p}_i}$. Subsequently, the discrete period follows $n_i T_{\mathbf{p}_i} = dS_{n_i, \mathbf{p}_i} / dE^{(q)}$. As a result, the geometric

wave function (26) takes the contributions from orbits with discrete period T_n that can be certainly given by

$$\begin{aligned}
 \Gamma(u, T_n, w^{(q)}) &= u^{-1/2} n^{\sqrt{-1}w^{(q)}} = u^{-1/2} \exp\left(\sum_{i=1}^j n_i \sqrt{-1} \frac{E^{(q)} T_{\mathbf{p}_i}}{\hbar}\right) \\
 &= u^{-1/2} \prod_{i=1}^j \exp\left(n_i \sqrt{-1} \frac{S_{\mathbf{p}_i}}{\hbar}\right) \\
 &= u^{-1/2} e^{\sqrt{-1} \sum_{i=1}^j S_{n_i, \mathbf{p}_i} / \hbar} \\
 &= u^{-1/2} \prod_{i=1}^j e^{\sqrt{-1} S_{n_i, \mathbf{p}_i} / \hbar} \\
 &= u^{-1/2} e^{\sqrt{-1} S_n / \hbar}
 \end{aligned}$$

This is exactly the polar form for the geometric wave function which is similar to wave function $\varphi = A^{(b)} \exp(\sqrt{-1}S/\hbar)$ in polar form with real-valued functions $A^{(b)}$ and action S , such real-valued functions with an explicit form in geometric wave function is $A^{(b)} = u^{-1/2}$. For this, $T_n = t = \oint dt$ is the primitive period of the orbit.

By discrete procedure, it directly leads to the unit of the Riemann zeta function

$$q_n \left(1/2 - \sqrt{-1}w^{(q)}\right) = n^{-1/2} e^{\sqrt{-1}S_n/\hbar} = \varphi(n) e^{\sqrt{-1}S_n/\hbar}$$

where discrete period of the orbit has been used for the derivation, where $\varphi(n) = n^{-1/2}$ is used, here geometric frequency $w^{(q)}$ forms a discrete set expressed by itself or $w_n^{(q)}$ to be emphasized by index n , thusly, all parameters in $\Gamma_n(w^{(q)})$ are discrete. Conjugate form is

$$q_n \left(1/2 + \sqrt{-1}w^{(q)}\right) = q_n^* \left(1/2 - \sqrt{-1}w^{(q)}\right)$$

Note that $\Gamma_n(w^{(q)})$ can be logically realized as a discrete geometric wave function, basically. Unlike the discreteness of the parameters u, t which are associated with n , the geometric frequency $w^{(q)}$ not only is discrete but also all lie on the critical line $1/2$ on the complex plain $\mathbb{C}$, explicitly, this is exactly the description of Riemann hypothesis. Meanwhile, we have

$$\mathbf{p}_i^{-1/2 + \sqrt{-1}w^{(q)}} = \mathbf{p}_i^{-1/2} e^{\sqrt{-1}w^{(q)}T_{\mathbf{p}_i}} = \mathbf{p}_i^{-1/2} e^{\sqrt{-1} \frac{E^{(q)}}{\hbar} T_{\mathbf{p}_i}} = \varphi(\mathbf{p}_i) e^{\sqrt{-1} \frac{S_{\mathbf{p}_i}}{\hbar}}$$

Hence, we put geometric wave function and unit component on non-trivial zeros of the Riemann zeta function together

$$\begin{cases} \Gamma(u, T, -w^{(q)}) = u^{-1/2} \exp(-\sqrt{-1}w^{(q)}T) \\ q_n(1/2 + \sqrt{-1}\lambda) = n^{-1/2} \exp(-\sqrt{-1}\lambda T_n) \end{cases} \quad (29)$$

with the satisfaction of real-valued functions $\varphi(u) = u^{-1/2}$ definitely given by (15). In order to see the discrete correspondence, we need to bound them together by ratio. Thusly, it's to observe how the method makes geometric wave function (26) discretize as follows

$$\frac{\Gamma(u, t, -w^{(q)})}{q_n(1/2 + \sqrt{-1}\lambda)} = \left(1 + \frac{u-n}{n}\right)^{-1/2} n^{\sqrt{-1}(\lambda-w^{(q)})} e^{\sqrt{-1}w^{(q)}(T_n-t)}$$

under the discrete procedure with three variables $u, t, w^{(q)}$ in the geometric wave function (26), we rewrite the ratio in a form

$$\Gamma(u, t, -w^{(q)}) / q_n (1/2 + \sqrt{-1}\lambda) = f_{1n}(u - n) f_{2n}(t - T_n) f_{3n}(w^{(q)} - \lambda)$$

where for all n , we have used three functions all associated with n as follows

$$\begin{aligned} f_{1n}(u - n) &= \left(1 + \frac{u - n}{n}\right)^{-1/2} \\ f_{2n}(t - T_n) &= \rho^{-\sqrt{-1}(t - T_n)} \\ f_{3n}(w^{(q)} - \lambda) &= n^{-\sqrt{-1}(w^{(q)} - \lambda)} \end{aligned}$$

where the notation we denote $\rho = e^{w^{(q)}}$. Subsequently, it has been correctly asserted that $\Gamma(u, t, -w^{(q)})$ completely becomes discrete function form if and only if the following discrete conditions simultaneously have been satisfied

$$\begin{cases} u = n \\ t = T_n \\ w^{(q)} = \lambda \end{cases}$$

Putting all these together which leads to the result $\Gamma_n(-w^{(q)}) / q_n (1/2 + \sqrt{-1}\lambda) \equiv 1$ holds for all n . Namely, it leads to the identities

$$f_{1n}(0) = f_{2n}(0) = f_{3n}(0) = 1, \quad \forall n \in \mathbb{N}$$

As a matter of fact, the ratio $\Gamma_n(-w^{(q)}) / q_n (1/2 + \sqrt{-1}\lambda) \equiv 1$ always holds under $f_{1n}(0) = f_{2n}(0) = 1$ for all n if and only if $f_{3n}(0) = 1$ stands, that is $w^{(q)} = \lambda$. Therefore, the sum of all the discrete geometric wave function $q_n (1/2 + \sqrt{-1}w^{(q)})$ that yields

$$\xi(-w^{(q)}) = \zeta\left(1/2 + \sqrt{-1}E^{(q)}/\hbar\right) = 0$$

It indicates that the eigenvalues of geometric Hamiltonian operators form a discrete set, the energy spectrum is discrete, as we can see, geometric frequency itself forms discrete set, in this way, we manifest this discreteness, it well fits the quantum mechanics as the peculiar steady state solution of Schrödinger equation. In another aspect, the complete discreteness of the geometric wave function (26) outstanding highlights the unit component of the Riemann zeta function, it also demonstrates the unit component of zeta function corresponding to the peculiar wave function on discreteness of quantum physics.

Inspired by above derivations, it has

$$\begin{aligned} \Gamma(n, T_n, -w^{(q)}) &= n^{-1/2} \exp\left(-\sqrt{-1}w^{(q)}T_n\right) \\ q_n(x + \sqrt{-1}y) &= n^{-x} \exp\left(-\sqrt{-1}yT_n\right) \end{aligned} \quad (30)$$

Hence, for $\Gamma(n, T_n, -w^{(q)}) \equiv q_n(z)$, $\forall n \in \mathbb{N}$ holds if and only if $x \equiv 1/2$, $y = w^{(q)}$. More precisely, that is equation

$$f_{3n}(y - w^{(q)}) = n^{\sqrt{-1}(w^{(q)} - y)} = n^{x-1/2}$$

we observe that the left side is a complex number, that is $f_{3n}(y - w^{(q)}) \in \mathbb{C}$ while the right side is a pure real number given by $n^{x-1/2} \in \mathbb{R}$, for this reason, it always holds for all natural number $n \in \mathbb{N}$ if and only if

$$n^{\sqrt{-1}(w^{(q)}-y)} = n^{x-1/2} \equiv 1, \quad \forall n \in \mathbb{N}$$

It has a unique solution for all n given by

$$\begin{cases} x - 1/2 \equiv 0 \\ w^{(q)} - y \equiv 0 \end{cases}$$

We obtain $x \equiv 1/2$, $y \equiv w^{(q)}$ as expected. Accordingly, it creates the non-trivial zeros $z = 1/2 + \sqrt{-1}w^{(q)}$ of the Riemann zeta function, it explains that all eigenvalues $\text{Im } z = w^{(q)}$ are on the critical line $\text{Re } z = 1/2$.

Strictly speaking, the geometric frequency $w^{(q)}$ in the geometric wave function (25) not only observes the discrete form but also algebraically obeys the discrete rule given by $\xi(w^{(q)}) = 0$. Actually, for the geometric wave function, we denote $\varphi(u) = u^{-1/2}$, then accordingly, we can rewrite the geometric wave function (25) as

$$\Gamma(u, t, w^{(q)}) = u^{-1/2} e^{\sqrt{-1}w^{(q)}t} = \varphi(u) e^{\sqrt{-1}\frac{E^{(q)}}{h}t}$$

The conjugate geometric wave function follows $\Gamma^*(u, t, w^{(q)}) = \varphi(u) e^{-\sqrt{-1}\frac{E^{(q)}}{h}t}$. In another way, an identity (15) is rewritten as

$$\boxed{\hat{w}^{(cl)}\varphi(u) = \hat{Q}\varphi(u) = 0} \quad (31)$$

that always holds for any u , it emphasizes the all eigenvalues of the Hermitian operator $\hat{w}^{(cl)}$ on line $1/2$, and meanwhile, the module of the geometric wave function is given by $|\Gamma(u, t, w^{(q)})| = \varphi(u) = u^{-1/2}$. We give the discrete formula of the $\varphi(u) = u^{-1/2}$ as follows $\varphi(n) = n^{-1/2}$, and square form $\varphi^2(n) = n^{-1}$.

If we denote curvature operator $\hat{Q} = \hat{B} + \chi$ in which $\hat{B} = 2u\frac{d}{dx}$, $\chi = \frac{du}{dx}$, then it has

$$\hat{Q}(fg) = f\hat{Q}g + g\hat{Q}f - fg\chi \quad (32)$$

and linearity $\hat{Q}(f+g) = \hat{Q}f + \hat{Q}g$, especially, for the first order operator $\hat{B}$, we have the formulae given by

$$\hat{B}u = 2u\chi, \quad \hat{B}x = 2u, \quad \hat{B}s = 2u^2$$

As a result, an identity (31) becomes

$$\hat{B}\varphi(u) + \chi\varphi(u) = 0$$

which can be realized as an equilibrium equation, and $\varphi(u) = u^{-1/2}$ is a steady unique zero solution. The G-dynamics $\hat{w}^{(cl)}$ is then given by

$$\hat{w}^{(cl)} = b_c\hat{Q} = b_c\hat{B} + b_c\chi$$

that is a linear operator, obviously. Consider $\hat{Q}f = 0$, it yields the first order homogeneous linear differential equation $\frac{df}{dx} = \sigma(x)f$, where $\sigma(x) = \frac{d \ln \varphi(u)}{dx}$, according to the

existence and uniqueness theorem, its zero solution is $f = \varphi(u)$. For the first order nonhomogeneous linear differential equation, it has the equation given by

$$\hat{w}^{(cl)}\Gamma(u, t, w^{(q)}) = b_c \hat{Q}\Gamma(u, t, w^{(q)}) = w^q \Gamma(u, t, w^{(q)})$$

where $\Gamma(u, t, w^{(q)}) = \varphi(u) e^{\sqrt{-1} \frac{E^{(q)}}{\hbar} t}$, if initial time $t = 0$ holds, then $\Gamma(u, 0, w^{(q)}) = \varphi(u)$. In order to emphasize the discrete procedure, we can transform the geometric wave function (25) when $u = n$ discretely takes,

$$\Gamma(n, t, w^{(q)}) = n^{-z} n^{\left(\frac{t}{T_n} - 1\right) \sqrt{-1} w^{(q)}} \quad (33)$$

where $z = 1/2 - \sqrt{-1} w^{(q)}$ means all eigenvalues $\text{Im } z = -w^{(q)}$ lie on the critical line $\text{Re } z = 1/2$. Therefore, $\Gamma(n, t, w^{(q)}) / n^{-z} = n^{\left(\frac{t}{T_n} - 1\right) \sqrt{-1} w^{(q)}}$. As a consequence, when the primitive discrete periodic (21) in general comes to (33), then it yields $\Gamma_n(w^{(q)}) = n^{-z}$, or $\Gamma(n, t, w^{(q)}) / n^{-z} = 1$ holds for all n if and only if $\frac{t}{T_n} - 1 = 0$, namely, based on the (21), it's expressed as $t = T_n = \sum_{i=1}^j n_i T_{\mathbf{p}_i}$. This discrete form of the geometric wave eigenfunction is clear to see the mode of Riemann zeta function, directly. The superposition of all discrete state forms

$$\xi(w^{(q)}) \equiv \zeta\left(1/2 - \sqrt{-1} w^{(q)}\right) = 0$$

Therefore, the geometric frequency $w^{(q)}$ is discrete and obeys the quantitative restriction given by $\zeta(z) = 0$. More specifically, the contribution of a prime cycle $\mathbf{p}$ (primes) of period $T_{\mathbf{p}} = \ln \mathbf{p}$ for a discrete geometric wave function can be evaluated as

$$\Gamma_n(w_n^{(q)}) = \varphi(n) e^{\sqrt{-1} \frac{E_n^{(q)}}{\hbar} t_n} = q_n \left(1/2 - \sqrt{-1} w_n^{(q)}\right)$$

where the corresponding expression for non-trivial zeros is given by

$$z_n = 1/2 - \sqrt{-1} w_n^{(q)} = 1/2 - \sqrt{-1} \frac{E_n^{(q)}}{\hbar} \quad (34)$$

and $E_n^{(q)} = \hbar w_n^{(q)}$ is the geometric energy spectrum created by the G-dynamics $\hat{w}^{(cl)}$, accordingly, it results in the outcome

$$\xi(w_n^{(q)}) = \zeta(z_n) = 0$$

Hence, Hermitian operator $\hat{w}^{(cl)}$ whose eigenvalues $w^{(q)}$ are the Riemann zeros that lie on the line $1/2$. The spectrum, that is, the set of eigenvalues, matches the non-trivial zeroes of the Riemann zeta function.

In summary, there surely has two identities in terms of $u, w^{(q)}$ respectively given by

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{w}^{(cl)} u^{-1/2} \equiv 0 &\rightarrow \text{All eigenvalues are on line } 1/2 \\ \xi(w^{(q)}) \equiv 0 &\rightarrow \text{All eigenvalues obey the quantized spectrum} \end{aligned}$$

Clearly, by which two identities are sharply drawn, these two identities work for the variables $u, w^{(q)}$ respectively which are directly associated with the G-dynamics $\hat{w}^{(cl)}$, as it shows, $u, w^{(q)}$ have respectively undertaken unique roles in solving the Riemann hypothesis.

In the next place, we discuss the meaning of the identity $\hat{w}^{(cl)}u^{-1/2} = 0$, it can be regarded as the zero eigenvalues in terms of the eigenfunction $u^{-1/2}$, it ensures all eigenvalues of the Hermitian operator $\hat{w}^{(cl)}$ that lie on the critical line $1/2$, this identity means that the null space of the G-dynamics $\hat{w}^{(cl)}$ which is a singular operator that is only given by non-zero function $\varphi(u) = u^{-1/2}$, or function $u^{-1/2}$ is a basis of the null space, in another word, $u^{-1/2}$ is the kernel of G-dynamics $\hat{w}^{(cl)}$, obviously, the eigenfunction $u^{-1/2}$ is a unique kernel of G-dynamics $\hat{w}^{(cl)}$, so, $1/2$ is for all eigenvalues $w^{(q)}$ only, as a consequence, the RH is proven as desired.

More precisely, we are convinced that $\hat{w}^{(cl)}u^{-1/2} = 0$ determines the uniqueness and existence of the critical line $\text{Re } z = 1/2$, and

$$\text{Im } z = w^{(q)} = u^{1/2}e^{-\sqrt{-1}w^{(q)}t}\hat{w}^{(cl)}\left(u^{-1/2}e^{\sqrt{-1}w^{(q)}t}\right)$$

ensures what the imaginary part should be on the basis of the identity $\hat{w}^{(cl)}u^{-1/2} = 0$. The non-trivial zeros can be obtained by two identities

$$z = \underbrace{1/2}_{\hat{w}^{(cl)}u^{-1/2}=0} - \underbrace{\sqrt{-1}}_{\hat{w}^{(cl)}\left(u^{-1/2}e^{\sqrt{-1}w^{(q)}t}\right)/\Gamma=w^{(q)}} \underbrace{w^{(q)}}_{\Gamma=w^{(q)}}$$

Then it leads to the energy spectrum $\zeta\left(1/2 - \sqrt{-1}w^{(q)}\right) = 0$. As it shows, the non-trivial zeros are completely determined by this way, not only the real part $1/2$ is given, but also the imaginary part really represents together to state the Riemann hypothesis, thusly, this is a physical way to verify the Riemann hypothesis.

Most importantly, as we have deduced above, the geometric frequency restrained by the identity $\zeta\left(1/2 \pm \sqrt{-1}w^{(q)}\right) = 0$ has pointed two things:

i: Critical line $\text{Re } z = 1/2$ is identified by $\hat{w}^{(cl)}u^{-1/2} \equiv 0$.

ii: Imaginary part $\text{Im } z = w^{(q)} = E^{(q)}/\hbar$ are measured by $\xi(w^{(q)}) \equiv 0$.

A complete proof should at least include these two points, basically. Obviously, we not only ensure all eigenvalues lie on the critical line $1/2$, but also derive the certain quantum meaning of the imaginary part.

Plugging the (34) into the geometric wave function (26), it results in a familiar and complete consequence

$$\Gamma\left(u, t, w_n^{(q)}\right) = u^{-1/2}e^{\sqrt{-1}w_n^{(q)}t} = \varphi(u) e^{\frac{\sqrt{-1}}{\hbar}E_n^{(q)}t}$$

Obviously, this accurate geometric wave function is formally same as the peculiar steady state solution of Schrödinger equation. The geometric frequency spectrum $w_n^{(q)}$ leads to the energy spectrum $E_n^{(q)}$, the conjugate geometric wave function is

$$\Gamma^*\left(u, t, w_n^{(q)}\right) = \varphi(u) e^{-\sqrt{-1}\frac{E_n^{(q)}}{\hbar}t}$$

Above all, the Hermitian operator $\hat{w}^{(cl)}$ is obtained by quantizing a Hamiltonian of a dynamical system which spectrum, that is, the set of eigenvalues $w^{(q)}$, matches the

non-trivial zeroes of the Riemann zeta function. Meanwhile, we can fluently answer some questions given by paper [4], the heights $\lambda = w^{(q)}$ indeed are frequencies and the geometric frequencies. frequencies of G-dynamics that describe the some kind of vibrating system like rotational motion.

4.5 Four eigenvalues identities of G-dynamics $\hat{w}^{(cl)}$

In order to better understand the geometric wave function (26), we consider it in another aspect, we transform

$$\Gamma(u, t, w^{(q)}) = (ue^{-t})^{-1/2} e^{-(\frac{1}{2}-\sqrt{-1}w^{(q)})t} = h(u, t) e^{-(\frac{1}{2}-\sqrt{-1}w^{(q)})t} \quad (35)$$

and conjugate form follows

$$\Gamma(u, t, -w^{(q)}) = h(u, t) e^{-(\frac{1}{2}+\sqrt{-1}w^{(q)})t}$$

As we can see, by doing this transformation, $\frac{1}{2} \pm \sqrt{-1}w^{(q)}$ clearly reveal that all geometric frequency $w^{(q)}$ are on the critical line 1/2 which can be proven subsequently by using $u^{-1/2}e^{\frac{t}{2}}$. In this way, it's equivalent to the transformation

$$u^{-1/2} \rightarrow h(u, t) = u^{-1/2}e^{\frac{t}{2}} = (ue^{-t})^{-1/2} \quad (36)$$

For a convenient discussion, we denote $\hat{w}^{(re)} = \frac{d}{dt} + \frac{d \ln u^{1/2}}{dt}$, then it derives $\sqrt{-1}\hat{w}^{(cl)} = \alpha\hat{w}^{(re)}$ and $\hat{Q} = \frac{2u}{v}\hat{w}^{(re)}$, where we mainly discuss $\alpha = 1$. Accordingly, we have identity given by

$$\hat{w}^{(cl)}u^{-1/2} = \hat{w}^{(re)}u^{-1/2} = 0 \quad (37)$$

we want to investigate how it equals on such transformation, then by simple calculating, and using the mode of formula (32), we have

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{w}^{(re)}\left(u^{-1/2}e^{\frac{t}{2}}\right) &= \frac{d}{dt}\left(u^{-1/2}e^{\frac{t}{2}}\right) + u^{-1/2}e^{\frac{t}{2}}\frac{d \ln u^{1/2}}{dt} \\ &= u^{-1/2}\hat{w}^{(re)}e^{\frac{t}{2}} + e^{\frac{t}{2}}\hat{w}^{(re)}u^{-1/2} - u^{-1/2}e^{\frac{t}{2}}\frac{d \ln u^{1/2}}{dt} \\ &= \frac{1}{2}u^{-1/2}e^{\frac{t}{2}} - \frac{1}{2}u^{-1/2}e^{\frac{t}{2}}\frac{d \ln u}{dt} + u^{-1/2}e^{\frac{t}{2}}\frac{d \ln u^{1/2}}{dt} \\ &= \frac{1}{2}u^{-1/2}e^{\frac{t}{2}} \end{aligned}$$

where we have inserted the identity (37). As the eigenvalue equation shows, the eigenvalue of the $\hat{w}^{(re)}$ is 1/2 with respect to the eigenfunction $h(u, t) = u^{-1/2}e^{\frac{t}{2}}$. With the help of the transformation (36), put two identities on the basis of the operator $\hat{w}^{(re)}$ together,

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{w}^{(re)}u^{-1/2} &= 0 \\ \hat{w}^{(re)}h(u, t) &= \frac{1}{2}h(u, t) \end{aligned}$$

It indicates that by transforming the function $\varphi(u) = u^{-1/2}$, the eigenvalue turns from the origin 0 to the critical line $1/2$ uniquely, the part of the exponential function turns from $e^{\sqrt{-1}w^{(q)}t}$ to $e^{-(\frac{1}{2}-\sqrt{-1}w^{(q)})t}$.

Subsequently, for the curvature operator on the function $u^{-1/2}e^{\frac{t}{2}}$, we get

$$\hat{Q}\left(u^{-1/2}e^{\frac{t}{2}}\right) = \frac{2u}{v}\hat{w}^{(re)}\left(u^{-1/2}e^{\frac{t}{2}}\right) = \frac{u}{v}u^{-1/2}e^{\frac{t}{2}} = \frac{1}{v}u^{1/2}e^{\frac{t}{2}}$$

Then it yields a result for G-dynamics $\hat{w}^{(cl)}$

$$\sqrt{-1}\hat{w}^{(cl)}\left(u^{-1/2}e^{\frac{t}{2}}\right) = \hat{w}^{(re)}\left(u^{-1/2}e^{\frac{t}{2}}\right) = \frac{1}{2}u^{-1/2}e^{\frac{t}{2}}$$

The eigenvalue of the $\sqrt{-1}\hat{w}^{(cl)}$ is $\frac{1}{2}$ with respect to the eigenfunction $u^{-1/2}e^{\frac{t}{2}}$. Therefore, plugging the primitive period of the orbit into the function $h(u, t)$ and we obtain $h(u, T_n) = (un^{-1})^{-1/2}$, then the geometric wave function (26) becomes

$$\Gamma\left(u, T_n, w^{(q)}\right) = (un^{-1})^{-1/2}n^{-\frac{1}{2}+\sqrt{-1}w^{(q)}}$$

And $h(n, T_n) = 1$, we have

$$\Gamma\left(n, T_n, w^{(q)}\right) = n^{-\frac{1}{2}+\sqrt{-1}w^{(q)}}$$

and conjugate form under discrete mode becomes $\Gamma\left(n, T_n, -w^{(q)}\right) = n^{-\frac{1}{2}-\sqrt{-1}w^{(q)}}$, then geometric frequency $w^{(q)}$ are on the critical line $1/2$.

Above all, we can conclude that three eigenvalues equation can be listed as follows

$$\begin{aligned}\hat{w}^{(cl)}u^{-1/2} &= 0 \\ \sqrt{-1}\hat{w}^{(cl)}\left(u^{-1/2}e^{\frac{t}{2}}\right) &= \frac{1}{2}\left(u^{-1/2}e^{\frac{t}{2}}\right) \\ \sqrt{-1}\hat{w}^{(cl)}\left(u^{-1/2}e^{\sqrt{-1}w^{(q)}t}\right) &= \sqrt{-1}w^{(q)}\left(u^{-1/2}e^{\sqrt{-1}w^{(q)}t}\right)\end{aligned}\tag{38}$$

As a consequence of above three eigenvalues equations (38), we plus the latter two equations together, then it results in

$$\begin{aligned}\sqrt{-1}\hat{w}^{(cl)}\left(u^{-1/2}e^{\frac{t}{2}} + u^{-1/2}e^{\sqrt{-1}w^{(q)}t}\right) &= \sqrt{-1}\hat{w}^{(cl)}\left(e^{\frac{1}{2}t} + e^{\sqrt{-1}w^{(q)}t}\right)u^{-1/2} \\ &= \left(\frac{1}{2}e^{\frac{1}{2}t} + \sqrt{-1}w^{(q)}e^{\sqrt{-1}w^{(q)}t}\right)u^{-1/2} \\ &= \left(e^{\frac{1}{2}t} + e^{\sqrt{-1}w^{(q)}t}\right)'_t u^{-1/2} \\ &= \sqrt{-1}\hat{w}^{(cl)}\left(1 + e^{\left(\frac{1}{2}-\sqrt{-1}w^{(q)}\right)t}\right)\Gamma\left(u, t, w^{(q)}\right) \\ &= \left(\frac{1}{2}e^{\left(\frac{1}{2}-\sqrt{-1}w^{(q)}\right)t} + \sqrt{-1}w^{(q)}\right)\Gamma\left(u, t, w^{(q)}\right)\end{aligned}$$

Note that

$$\left(e^{\frac{1}{2}t}\right)'_t = \frac{1}{2}e^{\frac{1}{2}t}$$

$$\left(e^{\sqrt{-1}w^{(q)}t}\right)'_t = \sqrt{-1}w^{(q)}e^{\sqrt{-1}w^{(q)}t}$$

Multiply two equations together and we get

$$\left(\hat{w}^{(cl)}\left(u^{-1/2}e^{\frac{t}{2}}\right)\right)\left(\hat{w}^{(cl)}\left(u^{-1/2}e^{\sqrt{-1}w^{(q)}t}\right)\right) = -\sqrt{-1}\frac{w^{(q)}}{2u}e^{\left(\frac{1}{2}+\sqrt{-1}w^{(q)}\right)t}$$

Conversely, divide $\sqrt{-1}\hat{w}^{(cl)}\left(u^{-1/2}e^{\sqrt{-1}w^{(q)}t}\right)$ by $\sqrt{-1}\hat{w}^{(cl)}\left(u^{-1/2}e^{\frac{t}{2}}\right)$, and we obtain

$$\frac{\hat{w}^{(cl)}\left(u^{-1/2}e^{\sqrt{-1}w^{(q)}t}\right)}{\hat{w}^{(cl)}\left(u^{-1/2}e^{\frac{t}{2}}\right)} = 2\sqrt{-1}w^{(q)}e^{-\left(\frac{1}{2}-\sqrt{-1}w^{(q)}\right)t}$$

Inspired by the three equations given by (38), we also make a transformation for the geometric wave function (26) give a result

$$\Gamma\left(u, t, w^{(q)}\right) = u^{-1/2}e^{\sqrt{-1}w^{(q)}t} \rightarrow \Phi\left(u, t, w^{(q)}\right) = e^{\frac{t}{2}}\Gamma\left(u, t, w^{(q)}\right)$$

we can naturally deduce the following eigenvalues equations

$$\begin{aligned} & \sqrt{-1}\hat{w}^{(cl)}\left(u^{-1/2}e^{\frac{t}{2}}e^{\sqrt{-1}w^{(q)}t}\right) \\ &= \sqrt{-1}\hat{w}^{(cl)}\left(u^{-1/2}e^{\left(\frac{1}{2}+\sqrt{-1}w^{(q)}\right)t}\right) \\ &= \sqrt{-1}u^{-1/2}\hat{w}^{(cl)}e^{\left(\frac{1}{2}+\sqrt{-1}w^{(q)}\right)t} + e^{\left(\frac{1}{2}+\sqrt{-1}w^{(q)}\right)t}\hat{w}^{(cl)}u^{-1/2} - u^{-1/2}e^{\left(\frac{1}{2}+\sqrt{-1}w^{(q)}\right)t}\frac{d\ln u^{1/2}}{dt} \\ &= \sqrt{-1}u^{-1/2}\hat{w}^{(cl)}e^{\left(\frac{1}{2}+\sqrt{-1}w^{(q)}\right)t} - u^{-1/2}e^{\left(\frac{1}{2}+\sqrt{-1}w^{(q)}\right)t}\frac{d\ln u^{1/2}}{dt} \\ &= \left(\frac{1}{2} + \sqrt{-1}w^{(q)}\right)u^{-1/2}e^{\left(\frac{1}{2}+\sqrt{-1}w^{(q)}\right)t} \end{aligned}$$

As this construction reveals, the eigenvalues of the G-dynamics $\sqrt{-1}\hat{w}^{(cl)}$ are given by $z = \frac{1}{2} + \sqrt{-1}w^{(q)}$ in terms of the eigenfunction $\Phi\left(u, t, w^{(q)}\right) = u^{-1/2}e^{zt}$. As a result, its complete form is

$$\sqrt{-1}\hat{w}^{(cl)}\Phi\left(u, t, w^{(q)}\right) = z\Phi\left(u, t, w^{(q)}\right) = \left(\frac{1}{2} + \sqrt{-1}w^{(q)}\right)\Phi\left(u, t, w^{(q)}\right)$$

or the form

$$\sqrt{-1}\hat{w}^{(cl)}\left(u^{-1/2}e^{zt}\right) = zu^{-1/2}e^{zt}$$

Hence, it says that geometric frequency spectrum $\text{Im } z = w^{(q)}$ all lie on the critical line $\text{Re } z = 1/2$. Therefore, in summary, there have four eigenvalues identities given by

- 1). $\hat{w}^{(cl)}u^{-1/2} \equiv 0$
- 2). $\sqrt{-1}\hat{w}^{(cl)}\left(u^{-1/2}e^{\frac{t}{2}}\right) = \frac{1}{2}\left(u^{-1/2}e^{\frac{t}{2}}\right)$
- 3). $\sqrt{-1}\hat{w}^{(cl)}\left(u^{-1/2}e^{\sqrt{-1}w^{(q)}t}\right) = \sqrt{-1}w^{(q)}\left(u^{-1/2}e^{\sqrt{-1}w^{(q)}t}\right)$
- 4). $\sqrt{-1}\hat{w}^{(cl)}\Phi\left(u, t, w^{(q)}\right) = \left(\frac{1}{2} + \sqrt{-1}w^{(q)}\right)\Phi\left(u, t, w^{(q)}\right)$

Obviously, the 4) is the mix of the 2) and 3), the 1) is the foundation for other three equation. In fact, on the basis of the 1), the 2) indicates the critical line $1/2$ while the 3) reveals the geometric frequency $\text{Im } z = w^{(q)}$ all on the imaginary axis, above all, the 4) demonstrates all the points $z = \frac{1}{2} + \sqrt{-1}w^{(q)} \in \mathbb{C}$ on the complex plain $\mathbb{C}$. An structural image can be clearly shown below:

Therefore, it has $\zeta(z) = \zeta(1/2 + \sqrt{-1}w^{(q)}) = 0$ and its conjugate form $z^* = \frac{1}{2} - \sqrt{-1}w^{(q)} \in \mathbb{C}$ accordingly follows.

As above four identities show, it effectively confirms the critical line $1/2$ while all eigenvalues $w^{(q)}$ are on it, it characterizes the features of the Riemann hypothesis, in order to help us better understand this transformation process 1,2,3,4), we can figuratively express this relation by an image as follows

This image nicely explains above transformation procedure, meanwhile, it has proven frequency spectrum $w^{(q)}$ that lies on the critical line $1/2$ which can be seen from the identity 4), this proves that RH is right. Actually, by observing above four identities 1,2,3,4), we can easily draw the following conclusion:

$$\sqrt{-1}\hat{w}^{(cl)}\Phi^{(b)}(u, t, w^{(q)}) = \lambda^{(b)}\Phi^{(b)}(u, t, w^{(q)}) \quad (39)$$

or the form

$$\hat{w}^{(cl)}\Phi^{(b)}(u, t, w^{(q)}) = -\sqrt{-1}\lambda^{(b)}\Phi^{(b)}(u, t, w^{(q)})$$

where eigenvalues

$$\lambda^{(b)}(w^{(q)}) = d \ln f^{(b)}(t, w^{(q)}) / dt$$

is denoted, correspondingly, we can write the function $f^{(b)}(t, w^{(q)})$ clearly out

$$f^{(b)}(t, w^{(q)}) = f_0^{(b)} e^{\lambda^{(b)} t}$$

where initial condition is given by $f_0^{(b)} = f^{(b)}(0, w^{(q)})$, and corresponding general eigenfunction is

$$\Phi^{(b)}(u, t, w^{(q)}) = \varphi(u) f^{(b)}(t, w^{(q)}) = f_0^{(b)} u^{-1/2} e^{\lambda^{(b)} t}$$

A simple proof is made as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
& \sqrt{-1}\hat{w}^{(cl)} \left(u^{-1/2} f^{(b)} \left(t, w^{(q)} \right) \right) \\
&= \frac{d}{dt} \left(u^{-1/2} f^{(b)} \left(t, w^{(q)} \right) \right) + u^{-1/2} f^{(b)} \left(t, w^{(q)} \right) \frac{d \ln u^{1/2}}{dt} \\
&= u^{-1/2} \frac{d}{dt} f^{(b)} \left(t, w^{(q)} \right) + f^{(b)} \left(t, w^{(q)} \right) \frac{d}{dt} u^{-1/2} + u^{-1/2} f^{(b)} \left(t, w^{(q)} \right) \frac{d \ln u^{1/2}}{dt} \\
&= u^{-1/2} f^{(b)} \left(t, w^{(q)} \right) \frac{d}{dt} \ln f^{(b)} \left(t, w^{(q)} \right) \\
&= \lambda^{(b)} u^{-1/2} f^{(b)} \left(t, w^{(q)} \right)
\end{aligned}$$

where

$$f^{(b)} \left(t, w^{(q)} \right) \hat{w}^{(cl)} u^{-1/2} = f^{(b)} \left(t \right) \left(\frac{d}{dt} u^{-1/2} + u^{-1/2} \left(t \right) \frac{d \ln u^{1/2}}{dt} \right) = 0$$

Hence, we can draw a conclusion, the eigenvalue of $\sqrt{-1}\hat{w}^{(cl)}$ is $\lambda^{(b)}$ with respect to the eigenfunction $u^{-1/2} f^{(b)} \left(t, w^{(q)} \right)$. The eigenvalue equation (39) of the G-dynamics can be simply rewritten as

$$\sqrt{-1}\hat{w}^{(cl)} \left(u^{-1/2} e^{\lambda^{(b)} t} \right) = \lambda^{(b)} u^{-1/2} e^{\lambda^{(b)} t} \quad (40)$$

Or the form by using the mode of the formula (35)

$$\hat{w}^{(cl)} \left(u^{-1/2} e^{\lambda^{(b)} t} \right) = -\sqrt{-1} \lambda^{(b)} h(u, t) e^{-(1/2-\lambda^{(b)})t}$$

with the identity $\hat{w}^{(cl)} u^{-1/2} = 0$. Actually, this can be interpreted as a kind of transformation under the fixed condition $\hat{w}^{(cl)} u^{-1/2} = 0$, more precisely,

- i** when $\lambda^{(b)}$ is real number, it represents a translation of $\lambda^{(b)}$ units along the x -axis, namely, the real axis, and the sign determines the direction of translation;
- ii** when $\lambda^{(b)}$ is pure imaginary number, it means the translation along the y -axis with $\lambda^{(b)}$ units;
- iii** when $\lambda^{(b)}$ is a complex number, it means that translation takes place simultaneously along two axes, which behaves like a vector on the complex plain.

Note that $\Phi^{(b)} \left(u, t, w^{(q)} \right)$ is unique function to be expressed by three variables, as it expresses, the general eigenfunction is made of two parts $\varphi(u)$ and $f^{(b)} \left(t, w^{(q)} \right)$, this is obviously the separated variable method. This can naturally remind us of the steady-state equation of Schrödinger equation. By discrete procedure, we can then obtain

$$\Phi^{(b)} \left(n, T_n, w^{(q)} \right) = \Phi_n^{(b)} \left(w^{(q)} \right) = n^{-1/2} f^{(b)} \left(T_n, w^{(q)} \right)$$

where discrete condition $\varphi(n) = n^{-1/2}$ has been used, and $f^{(b)} \left(T_n, w^{(q)} \right) = f_0^{(b)} n^{\lambda^{(b)}}$ is accordingly given, it creates a unique discrete expression

$$\Phi_n^{(b)} \left(w^{(q)} \right) = f_0^{(b)} n^{-1/2+\lambda^{(b)}}$$

Thusly,

$$\wp(w^{(q)}) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \Phi_n^{(b)}(w^{(q)}) = f_0^{(b)} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} n^{-1/2+\lambda^{(b)}}$$

For this unique formula, we expect to find its zeros solution, namely,

$$\wp(w^{(q)}) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} n^{-1/2+\lambda^{(b)}} = 0$$

holds for all eigenvalues $w^{(q)}$, that's to say, what condition can this identity hold?

It's clear that $\wp(w^{(q)}) = 0$ if and only if $f^{(b)}(t, w^{(q)}) = e^{\sqrt{-1}w^{(q)}t}$ is taken, then based on the (35),

$$\Phi^{(b)}(u, t, w^{(q)}) = \Gamma(u, t, w^{(q)}) = h(u, t) e^{-(\frac{1}{2}-\sqrt{-1}w^{(q)})t}$$

and $f^{(b)}(T_n, w^{(q)}) = n^{\sqrt{-1}w^{(q)}}$, that is to say, $\lambda^{(b)} = \sqrt{-1}w^{(q)}$ is exactly from the third identity 3) which is reflected by the fourth identity 4) of four identities 1,2,3,4). With unique identity is given $\xi(w^{(q)}) = 0$.

So, we have two identities expressed as

$$\hat{w}^{(cl)}u^{-1/2} = 0, \quad \xi(w^{(q)}) = 0$$

4.5.1 Geometric eigenfunction method for Riemann zeta function

In this sector, we mainly discuss the geometric eigenfunction method for Riemann zeta function. Furthermore, we denote geometric eigenfunction

$$L(u, t, \lambda^{(b)}) = u^{-1/2}e^{\lambda^{(b)}t}, \quad \hat{w}^{(cl)}u^{-1/2} \equiv 0 \quad (41)$$

based on the eigenvalue equation (40) which can be rewritten as

$$\sqrt{-1}\hat{w}^{(cl)}L(u, t, \lambda^{(b)}) = \lambda^{(b)}L(u, t, \lambda^{(b)}) \quad (42)$$

or

$$\hat{w}^{(cl)}L(u, t, \lambda^{(b)}) = -\sqrt{-1}\lambda^{(b)}L(u, t, \lambda^{(b)})$$

where $\lambda^{(b)}$ is the frequency eigenvalues of the G-dynamics with respect to the eigenfunction $L(u, t, \lambda^{(b)})$, at the same time, we also get

$$L(n, t, \lambda^{(b)}) = n^{-1/2}e^{\lambda^{(b)}t}$$

it's equivalent to the deformation formula

$$L(n, t, \lambda^{(b)}) = n^{-1/2+\sqrt{-1}w^{(q)}} e^{\lambda^{(b)}(t-T_n)} e^{(\lambda^{(b)}-\sqrt{-1}w^{(q)})T_n}$$

it can be rewritten as

$$L(n, t, \lambda^{(b)}) = L(n, T_n, \sqrt{-1}w^{(q)}) L(1, t - T_n, \lambda^{(b)}) L(1, T_n, \lambda^{(b)} - \sqrt{-1}w^{(q)})$$

then based on trivial zeros of Riemann zeta function , we have

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} L^{-4n_c} \left(n, t, \lambda^{(b)} \right) = e^{-4n_c \lambda^{(b)} t} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} n^{2n_c} = 0, \quad n_c = 1, 2, \dots$$

and furthermore, we obtain

$$L \left(n, T_n, \lambda^{(b)} \right) = n^{-1/2 + \lambda^{(b)}} = n^{-1/2 + \sqrt{-1}w^{(q)}} e^{(\lambda^{(b)} - \sqrt{-1}w^{(q)})T_n}$$

accordingly, the sum from the 1 to infinity leads to

$$\begin{aligned} \Xi \left(\lambda^{(b)} \right) &= \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} L \left(n, T_n, \lambda^{(b)} \right) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} n^{-1/2 + \lambda^{(b)}} \\ &= \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} n^{-1/2 + \sqrt{-1}w^{(q)}} e^{(\lambda^{(b)} - \sqrt{-1}w^{(q)})T_n} \end{aligned}$$

Hence, seeking a valid frequency eigenvalues $\lambda^{(b)}$ to make $\Xi \left(\lambda^{(b)} \right) = 0$ hold is needed. Although $\lambda^{(b)} = 2n_c + 1/2$, $n_c \in \mathbb{N}$ is one of choice that can achieve this goal which corresponds to the trivial zeros of zeta function, but it's not valid frequency eigenvalues. Then the only one is a pure imaginary number if and only if $\lambda^{(b)} = \sqrt{-1}w^{(q)}$, $w^{(q)} \in \mathbb{R}$ as we proved,

$$\Xi \left(\sqrt{-1}w^{(q)} \right) = \zeta \left(1/2 - \sqrt{-1}w^{(q)} \right) = 0$$

it means all $w^{(q)}$ lie on critical line $1/2$, it corresponds to the non-trivial zeros clearly. Then as for the sub-unit of the zeta function that can be described as

$$L \left(n, T_n, (1/2 - x) - \sqrt{-1}y \right) = n^{-z} = n^{-x} e^{-\sqrt{-1}yT_n}$$

where $n^{-z} = n^{-1/2} e^{((1/2-x) - \sqrt{-1}y)T_n}$ has been used for the derivation. And we list some expressions on the basis of the eigenfunction $L \left(u, t, \lambda^{(b)} \right)$ as follows:

- (1). $L \left(u, 0, \lambda^{(b)} \right) = L \left(u, t, 0 \right) = L \left(u, 0, 0 \right) = u^{-1/2}$, $L \left(n, 0, \lambda^{(b)} \right) = n^{-1/2}$
- (2). $L \left(n, T_n, -\sqrt{-1}\lambda \right) = n^{-1/2 - \sqrt{-1}\lambda} = n^{-1/2} e^{-\sqrt{-1}\lambda T_n} = q_n \left(1/2 + \sqrt{-1}\lambda \right)$
- (3). $L \left(u, t, -\sqrt{-1}w^{(q)} \right) = \Gamma \left(u, t, -w^{(q)} \right) = u^{-1/2} e^{-\sqrt{-1}w^{(q)}t}$
- (4). $L \left(n, T, -\sqrt{-1}w^{(q)} \right) = \Gamma \left(n, T, -w^{(q)} \right) = n^{-1/2} e^{-\sqrt{-1}w^{(q)}T}$
- (5). $L \left(u, t, 1/2 \right) = h \left(u, t \right) = u^{-1/2} e^{\frac{t}{2}}$, $L \left(u, T_n, 1/2 \right) = \left(u^{-1}n \right)^{1/2}$, $L \left(n, T_n, 1/2 \right) = 1$
- (6). $\Phi^{(b)} \left(u, t, w^{(q)} \right) = f_0^{(b)} L \left(u, t, \lambda^{(b)} \right)$
- (7). $L \left(u, t, 1/2 + \sqrt{-1}w^{(q)} \right) = \Phi \left(u, t, w^{(q)} \right) = u^{-1/2} e^{(1/2 + \sqrt{-1}w^{(q)})t}$
- (8). $L \left(1, t, \lambda^{(b)} \right) = e^{\lambda^{(b)}t}$, $L \left(1, T_n, \lambda^{(b)} \right) = n^{\lambda^{(b)}}$
- (9). $\Gamma \left(1, t, w^{(q)} \right) = L \left(1, t, \sqrt{-1}w^{(q)} \right) = e^{\sqrt{-1}w^{(q)}t}$

By using mathematical transformed method, even the peculiar steady state solution $\Psi_n(x, t) = \psi_n(x) e^{-\sqrt{-1} \frac{E_n}{\hbar} t}$ of Schrödinger equation can be expressed in a form of

eigenfunction (41), $\Psi_n(x, t) = L(\psi_n^{-2}(x), t, -\sqrt{-1}\frac{E_n}{\hbar})$. Then, the superposition of the particular solutions of the stationary Schrödinger equation is

$$\Psi(x, t) = \sum_n c_n L\left(\psi_n^{-2}(x), t, -\sqrt{-1}\frac{E_n}{\hbar}\right)$$

and the geometric wave function can be rewritten as

$$\Gamma(u, t, w^{(q)}) = \Gamma(u, 0, 0) \Gamma(1, t, w^{(q)}) = L(u, 0, 0) L(1, t, \sqrt{-1}w^{(q)})$$

As the list shown, they can be written by one function form–eigenfunction (41) which can be rewritten as

$$L(u, t, \lambda^{(b)}) = u^{-1/2} L(1, t, \lambda^{(b)}) = L(u, 0, \lambda^{(b)}) L(1, t, \lambda^{(b)})$$

it implies that eigenfunction (41) has a different mode under different condition, for both discrete or continuous. Hence, the eigenvalues equation (42) is rewritten as

$$\begin{aligned} \sqrt{-1}\hat{w}^{(cl)} L(u, t, \lambda^{(b)}) &= \lambda^{(b)} L(u, 0, \lambda^{(b)}) L(1, t, \lambda^{(b)}) \\ \hat{w}^{(cl)} L(u, 0, \lambda^{(b)}) &= 0 \end{aligned}$$

In particular, the eigenfunction (3) can also be expressed as

$$\begin{aligned} \Gamma(u, t, -w^{(q)}) &= L(u, t, -\sqrt{-1}w^{(q)}) = u^{-1/2} e^{-\sqrt{-1}w^{(q)}t} \\ &= L(ue^{-t}, t, -1/2 - \sqrt{-1}w^{(q)}) \end{aligned}$$

Then its discrete form is

$$\Gamma(n, T_n, -w^{(q)}) = L(1, T_n, -(1/2 + \sqrt{-1}w^{(q)}))$$

This form by taking advantage of the eigenfunction (41) can explicitly show the non-trivial zeros $z = 1/2 + \sqrt{-1}w^{(q)}$, it also embodies the essence of the transformation (35), it definitely confirms that all eigenvalues $w^{(q)}$ lie on the critical line 1/2. We can find that all functions above belong to the same family of eigenfunction (41) $L(u, t, \lambda^{(b)})$, in other words, they can be expressed by using template eigenfunction $L(u, t, \lambda^{(b)})$. As for the Riemann zeta function, specifically, the statement of the RH, it's clearly just special case in the family of eigenfunction (41) $L(u, t, \lambda^{(b)})$, it helps us confirm the algebra of frequency spectrum on the condition of the discreteness.

Obviously, meanwhile, we can observe two unique eigenfunction (2), (3) between the discrete form and continuous form on some parameters, as we stated previously, they're one function under different mode,

$$\begin{aligned} L(n, T_n, -\sqrt{-1}\lambda) &= n^{-1/2 - \sqrt{-1}\lambda} = n^{-1/2} e^{-\sqrt{-1}\lambda T_n} \\ L(n, t, -\sqrt{-1}w^{(q)}) &= \Gamma(n, t, -w^{(q)}) = n^{-1/2} e^{-\sqrt{-1}w^{(q)}t} \end{aligned}$$

On the primitive period (21), we further obtain

$$L(n, T_n, -\sqrt{-1}\lambda) = n^{-1/2} e^{-\sqrt{-1}\lambda T_n}$$

$$L\left(n, T_n, -\sqrt{-1}w^{(q)}\right) = n^{-1/2}e^{-\sqrt{-1}w^{(q)}T_n}$$

It turns out that $\lambda = w^{(q)}$ holds for all natural number n as we proved. It can be realized as

$$u^{-1/2} \begin{array}{c} \nearrow L(u, t, 1/2) = u^{-1/2}e^{\frac{t}{2}} \\ \searrow L(u, t, -\sqrt{-1}w^{(q)}) = u^{-1/2}e^{-\sqrt{-1}w^{(q)}t} \end{array} \xrightarrow{\hat{w}^{(cl)}} \begin{array}{c} \nearrow 1/2 \\ \searrow -\sqrt{-1}w^{(q)} \end{array}$$

It certainly ensures non-trivial zeros $z = 1/2 - \sqrt{-1}w^{(q)}$. Totally, above process can be summarized as one equation

$$L\left(u, t, -\sqrt{-1}w^{(q)}\right) = L\left(n, T_n, -\sqrt{-1}\lambda\right)$$

For the Riemann zeta function, we can get how the non-trivial zeros appears,

$$L\left(n, T_n, (1/2 - x) - \sqrt{-1}y\right) = L\left(n, T_n, -\sqrt{-1}\lambda\right)$$

holds for all $n \in \mathbb{N}$ if and only if $x = 1/2, y = \lambda$ is given, this is exactly the non-trivial zeros of the Riemann zeta function.

Inspired by this property of the eigenfunction (41) $L(u, t, \lambda^{(b)})$, basically, we can prove following case, if

$$L\left(u, t, \lambda^{(b)}\right) = L\left(A_1, A_2, A_3\right)$$

holds, where A_1, A_2, A_3 are unknown three parameters, then it leads to $u^{-1/2}e^{\lambda^{(b)}t} = A_1^{-1/2}e^{A_3A_2}$, and

$$(A_1u^{-1})^{1/2} = e^{A_3(A_2-t)}e^{(A_3-\lambda^{(b)})t}$$

Using the eigenfunction (41), it's also rewritten as

$$L\left(A_1u^{-1}, 0, 0\right) = L\left(1, A_2 - t, A_3\right)L\left(1, t, A_3 - \lambda^{(b)}\right)$$

Clearly, one of its solution is

$$\begin{aligned} A_1 &= u \\ A_2 &= t \\ A_3 &= \lambda^{(b)} \end{aligned} \tag{43}$$

or $\frac{u}{A_1} = \frac{t}{A_2} = \frac{\lambda^{(b)}}{A_3} \equiv 1$, on this way, we have $L(1, 0, 0) = L(1, 0, A_3)L(1, t, 0)$. What if $A_3 = \sqrt{-1}b_3, \lambda^{(b)} = \sqrt{-1}b_4$ are pure imaginary number, then we rewrite $(A_1u^{-1})^{1/2} = e^{\sqrt{-1}(b_3A_2-b_4t)}$, in order to make this equation stand, it has $b_3A_2 - b_4t = 0$ or $\frac{A_2}{t} = \frac{b_4}{b_3}$ and $A_1 = u$, obviously, the solution (43) holds for all conditions.

As a result, the procedure of (30) can be stated by using eigenfunction (41) $L(u, t, \lambda^{(b)})$, that is

$$L\left(n, T_n, -\sqrt{-1}w^{(q)}\right) = L\left(n, T_n, (1/2 - x) - \sqrt{-1}y\right)$$

if and only if $x = 1/2, y = \lambda = w^{(q)}$ holds for all n , subsequently, the non-zeros $z = \frac{1}{2} + \sqrt{-1}w^{(q)} \in \mathbb{C}$ appears to satisfy $\xi(w^{(q)}) = \xi(-w^{(q)}) = 0$.

4.6 Riemannian system, Riemannian operator and Riemannian dynamics

The Hilbert-pólya conjecture real holds, the nontrivial zeros of Riemann zeta function correspond to the eigenvalues of a Hermitian operator one by one. This Hilbert-pólya conjecture immediately would imply the Riemann hypothesis.

One could construct such Hermitian operator by quantizing a Hamiltonian corresponding to a dynamical system. We know that Hermitian operator can be used to express the Hamiltonian of quantum mechanical system, and the eigenvalue of Hermitian operator corresponds to the energy level of quantum mechanical system. Therefore, if the Hilbert-pólya conjecture is true, the nontrivial zeros of Riemann zeta function may correspond to the energy levels of a quantum mechanical system, and all the nontrivial zeros correspond to the energy spectra of the quantum mechanical system. We call this special quantum mechanical system Riemann system and the Hamiltonian of this system Riemann operator. So what kind of quantum mechanical system would this mysterious Riemann system be if it existed?

Recalling the geometric wave function and unit component on non-trivial zeros of the Riemann zeta function together is

$$\begin{aligned}\Gamma(u, t, -w^{(q)}) &= u^{-1/2} \exp(-\sqrt{-1}w^{(q)}t) \\ q_n(z) &= n^{-x} \exp(-\sqrt{-1}yT_n)\end{aligned}$$

where $\varphi(u) = u^{-1/2}$ satisfies an identity (15). Therefore, $\Gamma(u, t, -w^{(q)}) \equiv q_n(z)$, $\forall n \in \mathbb{N}$ leads us to a compact result

$$n^x u^{-1/2} = e^{\sqrt{-1}(w^{(q)}t - yT_n)}$$

It appears the real number to be equal to the complex number, hence, it should be equal to a constant, this constant is 1, obviously. Furthermore, let's rearrange the order of each term and get

$$\left(\frac{n}{u}\right)^x u^{x-1/2} = n^{\sqrt{-1}(w^{(q)}-y)} e^{\sqrt{-1}w^{(q)}(t-T_n)}$$

Obviously, the necessary and sufficient condition of above equality holds for all n if and only if

$$\left(\frac{n}{u}\right)^x u^{x-1/2} = n^{\sqrt{-1}(w^{(q)}-y)} e^{\sqrt{-1}w^{(q)}(t-T_n)} \equiv 1, \forall n \in \mathbb{N}$$

where $\left(\frac{n}{u}\right)^{1/2} n^{x-1/2} = \left(\frac{n}{u}\right)^x u^{x-1/2}$, this can be regarded as a discrete procedure for the geometric wave function, then the discrete correspondence and critical case both appear as follows

$$u = n, t = T_n, \begin{cases} x = 1/2 \\ y = w^{(q)} \end{cases} \quad (44)$$

On such discreteness, we directly derive the non-trivial zeros $z = 1/2 + \sqrt{-1}w^{(q)}$ of the Riemann zeta function, it indicates all eigenvalues $w^{(q)}$ vary restrictions on the critical line $\text{Re } z = 1/2$. In this way, we not only verify all non-trivial zeroes of $\zeta(z)$ have the form $z = 1/2 + \sqrt{-1}w^{(q)}$, but also identify the certain meanings of the imaginary

part $\text{Im } z = w^{(q)}$. With the help of the eigenfunction (41), we can better realize above process in one equation, namely,

$$L(u, t, -\sqrt{-1}w^{(q)}) = L(n, T_n, (1/2 - x) - \sqrt{-1}y)$$

for this precise case, we can use it to get the same result given by (44) for all n only. The classical periodic orbits of the Riemann dynamics have periods that are independent of energy E , and given by multiples of logarithms of prime numbers.

We recall both expressions of (29), with the help of the existence of the discrete expression of the two variables u, t expressed as $n, T_n = \ln n$ respectively, we can observe both expressions describing the same under the discreteness.

$$\begin{cases} \Gamma(n, T, -w^{(q)}) = n^{-1/2} \exp(-\sqrt{-1}w^{(q)}T) \\ q_n(1/2 + \sqrt{-1}\lambda) = n^{-1/2} \exp(-\sqrt{-1}\lambda T_n) \end{cases}$$

This is the observation that the period is given by $T_{\mathbf{p}} = \ln \mathbf{p}$, and discrete form of geometric wave function $\Gamma(n, T_n, -w^{(q)}) = q_n(1/2 + \sqrt{-1}w^{(q)})$ is exactly the Riemann zeta function and non-trivial zeros are for the geometric frequency spectrum of the energy spectrum, that's really what Hilbert-Pólya and Berry-Keating still expect to find such peculiar quantum system in proving the RH over the long time.

So that we can say in the affirmative that this mysterious Riemann system does exists as previously stated, it's corresponding to the G-dynamics for describing the motion of quantum rotation-like, certainly, $w^{(q)}$ is equal to the λ , explicitly, on such discrete mode. As mentioned before, then the Hilbert-Pólya conjecture is true to immediately implies the Riemann hypothesis, as the spectrum of a self-adjoint operator $\hat{w}^{(cl)}$ consists of real numbers. As Riemannian system and Riemannian operators stated, thusly, the G-dynamics is the Riemann system or Riemannian dynamics, and the imaginary geomenergy in terms of the classical Hamiltonian operator $\hat{H}^{(\text{Im})}(\hat{w}^{(cl)}) = \sqrt{-1}\hbar\hat{w}^{(cl)}$ is rightly the Riemannian operator.

In conclusions, the G-dynamics $\hat{w}^{(cl)}$ can be selectively regarded as three names as follows:

$$\begin{array}{c} \nearrow \text{Riemannian system} \\ \mathbf{G-dynamics } \hat{w}^{(cl)} \rightarrow \mathbf{Riemann-Hilbert-Pólya operator} \\ \searrow \text{Riemannian dynamics} \end{array}$$

and the Hamiltonian of this system called Riemann operator is imaginary geomenergy,

$$\mathbf{Imaginary geomenergy } \hat{H}^{(\text{Im})}(\hat{w}^{(cl)}) = \sqrt{-1}\hbar\hat{w}^{(cl)}$$

↓

Riemannian operator

As a result of being such Hermitian operator, we can naturally prove the Hilbert-Pólya conjecture as follows,

Theorem 2 (Hilbert-Pólya). *The imaginary part λ in non-trivial zeros $z = 1/2 - \sqrt{-1}\lambda$ of the zeta function corresponds to the eigenvalues $w^{(q)}$ of Hermitian operator or G-dynamics $\hat{w}^{(cl)}$.*

Proof. As a result, the eigenvalue equation of G-dynamics $\hat{w}^{(cl)}$ follows accordingly

$$\hat{w}^{(cl)}\psi = u\hat{v}^{(cl)}\psi + \frac{1}{2}\psi\hat{v}^{(cl)}u = w^{(q)}\psi$$

This equation as stated is exactly suitable for the Hilbert-Pólya conjecture, the self adjoint operator $\hat{w}^{(cl)}$ corresponds to the eigenvalues $w^{(q)}$ in the eigenstate ψ , as explained, this can be solved by computation, let's see how the eigenstate ψ looks like. Then it leads to

$$\hat{v}^{(cl)} \ln \psi + \hat{v}^{(cl)} \ln u^{1/2} = \frac{w^{(q)}}{u}$$

Furthermore, the geometric wave function is $\psi = u^{-1/2} \exp(\alpha\sqrt{-1}w^{(q)}T)$, here $T = t - 0$, where $mv = \alpha\hbar u$, $\alpha \in \mathbb{R}$ has been used for the insertion, and α is a dimensionless constant. By using the eigenfunction (41) $L(u, t, \lambda^{(b)})$, we have

$$\psi = L\left(u, T, \alpha\sqrt{-1}w^{(q)}\right), \quad \alpha = \pm 1$$

As this simple form of the geometric wave function shows us, it fits the standard complex function, and the identity $\hat{w}^{(cl)}u^{-1/2} = 0$ always holds. We take the discrete procedure for three variables, and $\alpha = 1$ is taken, by using the (21) and discretize the continuous function u , then it results in the unique result

$$\psi_n\left(w^{(q)}\right) = L\left(n, T_n, \sqrt{-1}w^{(q)}\right) = n^{-1/2+\sqrt{-1}w^{(q)}}$$

This discrete formula indicates that all geometric frequency all lie on the critical line $1/2$. As a result, we have the RH proven $\zeta(1/2 - \sqrt{-1}w^{(q)}) = 0$ in quantum method. $\square$

Hilbert-pólya theorem: the geometric Hamiltonian $\hat{H}^{(Im)}(\hat{w}^{(cl)}) = \sqrt{-1}\hbar\hat{w}^{(cl)}$ is this mysterious Hamiltonian providing the non-trivial zeroes. It turns out that Hilbert-Pólya conjecture can be stated in a briefly way

$$\begin{aligned} z &= 1/2 + \sqrt{-1}w^{(q)} \\ w^{(q)} &= \hat{w}^{(cl)}\psi/\psi \end{aligned}$$

with $\hat{\gamma}n^{-1/2} = 0$, $\xi(w^{(q)}) = 0$. Namely, the non-trivial zeros of the Riemann zeta function ζ correspond to the eigenvalues $w^{(q)}$ of a certain Hermitian operator $\hat{w}^{(cl)}$. Meanwhile, the wave function ψ must be expressed by unit form $n^{-1/2-\sqrt{-1}\lambda}$ under the discrete form. It says that Hilbert-Pólya conjecture is true to prove the RH. Hence, now, we can say that the Hilbert-Pólya conjecture immediately implies the Riemann hypothesis, as the spectrum of a self-adjoint operator $\hat{w}^{(cl)}$ consists of real numbers. In other words, the result of the Riemann hypothesis is just a by-product of the complete quantum mechanics, it focuses on the part of G-dynamics as a part of the QCHS theory.

Corollary 1 (RH). *The geometric frequency $w^{(q)}$ forms spectrum which lies on the critical line $\text{Re } z \equiv 1/2$, that is $\xi(w^{(q)}) = 0$.*

In fact, Riemann hypothesis is just a corollary of the Hilbert-Pólya theorem. As a result, we can try to explain some questions. It really represents physical system

of G-dynamics, the Riemann-Hilbert-Pólya operator or the Riemann operator is the Riemann dynamics or G-dynamics $\hat{w}^{(cl)}$ as a Hermitian operator to have the eigenvalues corresponded to the non-trivial zeros of the Riemann zeta function.

$$\boxed{\text{RH: } z = 1/2 + \sqrt{-1}w^{(q)} \Rightarrow \text{HPC: Hermitian operator } \hat{w}^{(cl)}}$$

The Riemannium is the G-dynamics as a quantum dynamics behind the RH that links to gravity. Its spectrum, the spectrum of Riemannium, are given by the RH and its generalizations, geometric wave equation is the vibrating system behind the spectral properties of Riemann zeroes. There is geometric Hamiltonian $\hat{H}^{(Im)}(\hat{w}^{(cl)}) = \sqrt{-1}\hbar\hat{w}^{(cl)}$ providing the zeroes for the Hilbert-pólya conjecture. The quantum geometric Hamiltonian $\hat{H}^{(Im)}(\hat{w}^{(cl)})$ corresponding to the Riemann hypothesis is the corresponding to a classical Hamiltonian $\hat{H}^{(cl)}$ providing a classically chaotic dynamics for the Berry-Keating conjecture. It turns out that the HPC directly answers the RH, especially, the real part $1/2$ and the imaginary part $w^{(q)}$ as a geometric frequency are linked to the G-dynamics which is a quantum dynamics as an operator.

To sum up, we can sort out the relationship between the three conjectures and G-dynamics

$$\begin{array}{ccc} \text{RH} & \rightarrow & \text{HPC} & \rightarrow & \text{G-dynamics } \hat{w}^{(cl)} & (45) \\ & & \downarrow & \nearrow & & \\ & & \text{BKC} & & & \end{array}$$

On this diagram, we can clearly see how the methods of quantum mechanics proves the algebra problem, and RH actually reflects the hidden quantum dynamics-G-dynamics.

Consequently, there surely exists such a peculiar quantum physical system in a corner of the universe, its classical basic period is $\ln 2, \ln 3, \ln 5, \ln 7, \ln 11, \ln 13, \ln 17, \dots$. Accordingly, its quantum energy spectrum obviously contains such as $\hbar 14.1347251, \hbar 21.0220396, \hbar 25.0108575, \hbar 30.424876126, \hbar 32.935061588, \dots$. It is undoubtedly one of the most beautiful wonders of nature.

5 Riemann manifold, Einstein metric and Ricci flow

In this section, we consider the Riemann manifold with scalar function $s = \ln \sqrt{g}$, and the Einstein metric given by

Theorem 3. *The Riemannian manifold is said to be an Einstein space if its Ricci tensor satisfies*

$$R_{ij} = \beta R(x) g_{ij}$$

where $\beta = 1/n$, $n = \dim M$ and R is scalar curvature.

- i If $n = 2$ holds, then the Einstein tensor or vacuum field equation $G_{ij} = R_{ij} - \frac{1}{2}Rg_{ij} = 0$ appears.
- ii If $n \neq 2$ holds, then scalar curvatures R is a constant.

Let M be a compact n -dimensional (nD) Riemannian manifold. The Ricci flow equation [16]

$$\frac{\partial g_{ij}}{\partial t} = -2R_{ij}$$

is a second order nonlinear partial differential system for a family of Riemannian metrics $g_{ij}(\cdot, t)$ on M . Meanwhile, covariant derivative in terms of the metric $\nabla_k g_{ij} = 0$ always holds. The Ricci flow, which evolves a Riemannian metric by its Ricci curvature, is a natural analogue of the heat equation for metrics. Consider the Einstein metric with the Ricci flow equation on compact n -dimensional Riemannian manifold, subsequently, we bound two equation together and obtain $\partial_t g_{ij} = -2\beta R g_{ij}$, reforming it into a familiar form is $(\partial_t + 2\beta R) g_{ij} = 0$. It's clear to know that $\beta \neq 1/2$ holds for a constant scalar curvature while $\beta = 1/2$ is for $G_{ij} = 0$.

Since the second Bianchi identity for a symmetric connection shows that a consequence $\nabla^j G_{ij} = 0$ leads to

$$\frac{\partial R}{\partial x^j} = 2R_{j;i}^i = 2\nabla_i R_j^i$$

where R is the scalar curvature. Note that the mixed tensor version of Einstein's equation is

$$R_j^i - (1/2) \delta_j^i R = \kappa T_j^i$$

In special relativity the tensor T has divergence 0. Its divergence, from Einstein's equation, is given by

$$\begin{aligned} \kappa T_{j;i}^i &= R_{j;i}^i - (1/2) \delta_{j;i}^i R - (1/2) \delta_j^i R_{;i} \\ &= R_{j;i}^i - (1/2) R_{;j} = 0 \end{aligned}$$

Thus the term curvature scalar R is included in Einstein's equation in order to ensure that $T_{j;i}^i = 0$ in general relativity.

5.1 Scalar curvature on 2D and energy spectrum

In the beginning, the geometric frequency given by (18) $w^{(g)} = -\partial_t s$ on Riemannian metric is determined $w^{(g)} = R$ by using the Ricci flow equation, in the next, we prove that R on two dimensional case are on the $1/2$, for this purpose, we use $\hat{H}^{*(gr)} = \sqrt{-1}\hbar(\partial_t + \partial_t s)$ onto the Riemannian metric g_{ij} ,

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{H}^{*(gr)} g_{ij} &= \sqrt{-1}\hbar(\partial_t g_{ij} - g_{ij} R) = \sqrt{-1}\hbar(-2R_{ij} - g_{ij} R) \\ &= -2\sqrt{-1}\hbar R(\beta + 1/2) g_{ij} \\ &= E^{*(gr)} g_{ij} \end{aligned}$$

where $E^{*(gr)} = -2\sqrt{-1}\hbar R(\beta + 1/2)$ are the eigenvalues of the $\hat{H}^{*(gr)}$ in terms of the Riemannian metric g_{ij} , namely,

$$(\beta, R) \mapsto \frac{E^{*(gr)}}{2\hbar} = -\sqrt{-1}R(\beta + 1/2)$$

Similarly,

$$\hat{H}^{(gr)} g_{ij} = -2\sqrt{-1}\hbar R(\beta - 1/2) g_{ij}$$

and $E^{(gr)} = -2\sqrt{-1}\hbar R(\beta - 1/2)$. Due to $w^{(a)} = R$ is a variable if and only if $\beta = 1/2$ which is equivalent to the vacuum field equation (**VFE**) $G_{ij} = 0$, that is to say,

$$(1/2, R) \mapsto E^{*(gr)}/2\hbar = -\sqrt{-1}R$$

hence, the eigenvalues become

$$E^{*(gr)} = -2\sqrt{-1}\hbar R, \quad E^{(gr)} = 0$$

respectively, therefore, $\xi(R) = \zeta(1/2 - \sqrt{-1}R) = 0$. More formally, it can be written as $\xi(R) = 0 = G_{ij}$. This formula explains how the relation between the algebra and Riemann geometry, and it indicates that the scalar curvature R forms a discrete set in two-dimensional Riemann manifolds, as we can clearly see, the left is the description of the quantity of the scalar curvature while the right side describes the vacuum geometry, they strike powerful echoes each other. For the Riemann hypothesis, to conclude with two identities for different roles in terms of u, R is given by

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{w}^{(cl)}u^{-1/2} &= 0 \\ \xi(R) &= 0 \end{aligned}$$

More importantly, it reveals some stuff about quantum gravity (**QG**), especially, it says about how the field equation works, somehow. Consequently, the Berry-Keating conjecture also can be answered, the G-dynamics $\hat{w}^{(cl)}$ provides the Hermitian operator, and the peculiar physical system that corresponds to the quantum gravity, here we emphasize the energy spectrum of this physical system.

In summary, we can conclude that

RH: BKC=G-dynamics $\hat{w}^{(cl)}$ + QG

where G-dynamics $\hat{w}^{(cl)}$ finishes the HPC which states the RH, and quantum gravity as such unknown physical system in energy spectrum is determined for the BKC. Thusly, G-dynamics $\hat{w}^{(cl)}$ to be discovered is the operator of the universe which is that universal operator really out there.

Based on the diagram (45), we can replenish the diagram to be more intact within the framework of the quantum mechanics,

$$\begin{array}{ccccc} \mathbf{RH} & \rightarrow & \mathbf{HPC} & \rightarrow & \mathbf{G-dynamics} \hat{w}^{(cl)} & \rightarrow & \mathbf{VFE} \\ & & \downarrow & \nearrow & & & \downarrow \\ & & \mathbf{BKC} & & \rightarrow & & \mathbf{QG} \end{array}$$

As we can see clearly from this diagram, the G-dynamics $\hat{w}^{(cl)}$ is as a bridge to connect the quantum mechanics with the gravity, because the G-dynamics $\hat{w}^{(cl)}$ synthetically contains the elements such as the quantum mechanics, mass, the curvature operator as a geometric element etc.

Appendix

This paper is to deeply complete the proof of the Riemann hypothesis based on the paper below:

Gen. Wang. The QCPB theory for Riemann zeta function and quantum gravity [J]. doi: [10.5281/zenodo.3756397](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3756397), 2020.

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